

KAABAG: AN EXPLORATORY STUDY ON SOCIAL SUPPORT TO DRUG SURRENDERERS OF THE COMMUNITY-BASED REHABILITATION PROGRAM

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Kaabag: An Exploratory Study on Social Support to Drug Surrenderers of the Community-Based Rehabilitation Program

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Abstract

This study thus explores and identified the social support to drug surrenderers of the community-based rehabilitation program at the Municipality of Baungon, Province of Bukidnon. Using a mixed-methods research design, data was collected through a survey-questionnaire, in-depth interviews, and focus group discussions from 142 drug surrenderers. The drug-surrenderers are mostly between 30 and 39 years old, married, with three to four children and low-skilled workers. Majority are high school graduates, thirteen of them were degree holders, and Roman Catholics. Data shows that the drug-surrenderers reports high level of emotional support from friends, significant other, and family. This strengthens the facts that friends, significant other, and family play a critical role in the recovery process of drug surrenderers. The study also found that age, civil status, educational attainment, and gender have a significant impact on perceived social support that shows that people have different attitude and treatment given to drug surrenderers according to their age bracket, civil status and educational attainment. While membership in organization did not show any significant difference on perceived social support. Thus, it is recommended that Community-based rehabilitation program in Baungon should continue to provide services to drug surrenderers. The government and non-government organizations may also work hand-in-hand to fight drug addiction in the country.

Keywords: *kaabag, social support, drug surrenderers, community-based rehabilitation program*

Introduction

The Philippines has a long history of drug trafficking and abuse. In response to this concern, Presidential Decree No. 1866, also known as the Dangerous Drugs Act of 1972, was enacted to address the drug problem in the country. The law harshly punishes people who sell drugs, and drug traffickers will be on death warrants. Even though the government is trying to stop drug trafficking, the problem still exists (Cayetano, Sotto, and Duterte, 2021).

The unresolved serious drug-related problems led to the drastic “war on drugs” act by former President Rodrigo Duterte. In response to the government's crackdown, many people who use or sell drugs have decided to turn themselves in. As of September 2017, the Philippine National Police (PNP) reported that more than 700,000 drug users and pushers have surrendered to the authorities.

These drug surrenderers used drugs and surrendered during the Anti-Illegal Drugs Campaign. It was during this campaign project that “Tokhang” and “Hight Valued Target Tokhang” or “knock and plead” was launched by the Philippine National Police to target the drug-infected barangays. In coordination with the local government unit through the Philippines Dangerous Drugs Act of 2002 (Republic Act No. 9165) and the Philippines Local Government Code (Republic Act No. 7160), this was reinforced by Executive Order No. 4 of 2016 to provide establishment and support of drug misuse treatment and rehabilitation facilities nationwide (Dangerous Drug Board 2020).

While the government has welcomed drug surrenderers, they face many challenges. They often find it difficult to find employment, as many employers are reluctant to hire them due to the stigma attached to drug users. The United Nations Sustainable Health (2023) implemented the Sustainable Development Goal number 3, which aims to ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all ages, focusing on reducing the burden of disease and improving access to quality healthcare.

Escabel et al. (2015) presented four strategies to eliminate drug-related problems. First is the preparation and support for the drug personalities who surrender for their reintegration into the community. Second, the friends, significant other, family, and community involvement during the stay-in program positively affect drug surrenderers. Third is community support and participation, a patient-centered mode of therapeutic interaction that facilitates support and makes treatment more expedient if community members comprehend the situation. Last but not least is the partnership with stakeholders and the community to support the restoration of the health of drug surrenderers, as this requires a collaborative effort and cross-sectorial cooperation.

The community-based rehabilitation program takes a holistic approach to rehabilitating the surrendered drug personalities. By examining the social support provided to drug surrenderers, this paper can contribute to understanding the role of community-based rehabilitation programs in promoting justice, peace, and influential institutions in addressing drug-related issues as the aims of the Sustainable Development Goal # 16 on peace, justice, and strong institutions (United Nations, 2015).

Right after the community-based rehabilitation program, social support is vital in effectively treating drug surrenderers. This social support is the support they can get from their friends, significant others, and family (emotional support), as well as the support from their barangay, local government unit, and membership in an organization (instrumental support). As the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services (2019) mentioned, social support is the most effective yet accessible strategy for people with drug-related

problems.

Social support can help a drug surrenderer maintain a greater perspective and increase self-assurance where we have someone to rely on in difficult situations and improve life satisfaction to be resilient, especially during recovery. The Sustainable Development Goal 4: Quality education suggests that this paper could contribute to understanding the social support needs of drug surrenderers in community-based rehabilitation programs. This knowledge can help inform educational interventions and programs to support these individuals (United Nations, 2015).

The drug surrenderer can cope with their condition through positive social support. Social support from their friends, significant other, family, and community are the great factors to consider for a successful treatment process for drug-addicted individuals. It is a perception and a reality that a person believes in that they can get assistance from others through their social network (Liu et al., 2018).

Thus, social support may be essential to drug surrenderers, especially when they have drug use problems. So it is crucial to know how social support plays a vital role in drug surrenderers' recovery process, particularly when they undergo a Community-Based Rehabilitation program.

Knowing the importance of Community-Based Rehabilitation and its effects, thus is a need to study how it works in Baugon, Bukidnon. Data about the Community-Based Rehabilitation Program drug surrenderers in Baugon, Bukidnon, are still lacking. The Municipal Anti-Drug Abuse Council (MADAC) has no concrete and available data on the micro-level, and macro-social support drug surrenderers receive right after completing the community-based rehabilitation program.

So, there is a need to study this research problem and find out what is going on with the people who turn in drugs to answer the research gap. Through this study, the researcher explored the micro-level of support (emotional support) and macro-support (instrumental support) to understand the kind of social support they most received and their experiences as drug surrenderers after a rehabilitation program in Baugon, Bukidnon. It intends that the result of this study will give the drug surrenderers a better perspective on risk factors and lousy behavior due to drug use and thus will serve as their guide to accomplish a lifelong recovery process and find their purpose and meaning in life and proposed that data from this study will add more information and understanding for the workers of the Community-Based Rehabilitation Program and help enhance the said program for the benefit of everybody.

Research Questions

The study explored and identified the social support of drug surrenderers in the community-based rehabilitation program of Baugon Bukidnon. Specifically, the study attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents?
2. What is the level of perceived social support of drug surrenderers according to:
 - 2.1. Micro-Level Social Support (Emotional Support)
 - 2.1.1. friends;
 - 2.1.2. significant other; and
 - 2.1.3. family?
3. What is the Social Support received by drug surrenderers according to:
 - 3.1. Macro Social Support (Instrumental Support)
 - 3.1.1. barangay;
 - 3.1.2. local government unit; and
 - 3.1.3. membership in the organization?
4. Is there a significant difference between drug surrenderers' perceived social support according to:
 - 4.1. age;
 - 4.2. civil status;
 - 4.3. educational attainment;
 - 4.4. gender; and
 - 4.5. membership in the organization?
5. How does social support affect drug surrenderers' recovery process?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used mixed-method used to analyze both qualitative data and quantitative data. The exploratory sequential approach described by Berman (2017) consists of an initial qualitative phase of data collection and analysis, a quantitative stage, and a final phase of integrating or linking data from the two independent strands of data.

The mixed-method approach integrates qualitative and quantitative data to describe research issues meaningfully. Employing mixed methods enables researchers to answer research questions with adequate depth and breadth and facilitates the generalization of findings and implications of examined matters to the entire community (Dawadi et al., 2021).

The researcher developed unique research questions for qualitative data to capture the essence and experiences of drug surrenderers. These questions primarily focused on drug surrenderers' emotional and instrumental social support. It also includes questions about the effects of social support on drug surrenderers' recovery process.

An in-depth interview, also known as a one-on-one interview, is a method for gathering data was more thorough information or a deeper understanding of a subject or concept. The participant in an in-depth interview was encouraged and supported to talk in-depth about the issue under study. In-depth discussion was one of the most efficient methods of obtaining primary data. One of the most crucial advantages of an in-depth interview was that it helped uncover more detailed and in-depth information than other data collection methods like surveys (Showkat & Parveen, 2017).

The researcher began the in-depth interview with an orientation of the interviewee's background, the interview's goal, and the study's objectives, as well as a check of the audio functionality of the recorder. The researcher avoided directly asking hard-hitting questions and instead built a pleasant environment before giving questions one at a time to give participants sufficient time to think and recall their experiences. To record the participant's experiences completely, the interviewee focused 90% of her concentration on listening and 10% on speaking but clarified some unclear answers.

Also, the researcher did not ask sensitive questions that could affect the participant's religion, social life, politics, economics, or morals. The researcher began asking hard-hitting questions when recognizing that the environment had become viable. If a participant needed help comprehending the question, the researcher reformulated it and asked it differently.

When a participant said something irrelevant or unrelated to the topic, the researcher attempted to bring them back to the topic subtly and addressed all ethical concerns. Lastly, the participant asked whether they wished to contribute anything. The researcher interviewed the participants exhaustively about their experiences with the given topic. The study also conducted focus-group discussions with the five randomly selected participants. A focus group is an in-depth interview conducted in a group setting, whose sessions have predetermined parameters regarding the proposal, size, makeup, and interview processes. During the discussion, individuals influence one another by responding to ideas and contributions.

The researcher provided open-ended questions to create responses and foster discussion among the participants. "The goal of the researcher in a focus group discussion was to develop as many arguments and opinions as possible in a limited amount of time and researcher want a more in-depth explanation of a problem or topic than a questionnaire can provide (Mishra, 2016)."

In conducting the focus group discussion, the researcher started by determining the topic and goal of the focus group discussion, including the potential participants. Furthermore, the researcher chose a suitable location for the focus group, which was scheduled to last 90-120 minutes and led by the researcher. "Focus group data collection requires verifying audio records, evaluating written letters, acquiring and identifying supplementary resources, and requiring exceptional concepts and ideas (Tümen Akyildiz, 2021)."

The data from in-depth interviews and focus group discussions were processed using thematic analysis. Thematic analysis is looking at qualitative data to find patterns or themes. Braun and Clarke (2006) claimed that it should be the first qualitative method studied because it teaches essential skills that can use in many other types of analysis. There is a six-step method for this kind of investigation these were: familiarize with the data, start to generate codes, search for themes, examine topics, define themes, and lastly, write up.

The thematic analysis aimed to find themes or important, relevant patterns in the data and then use these themes to answer research questions or comment on a topic. A robust thematic analysis does much more than summarize the data; it analyzes and makes meaning of it (Stranges et al., 2014).

Participants

The subject participants of the study were the 142 drug surrenderers from the ten barangays of Baungon. The 142 drug surrenderers were determined by the Municipal Anti-Drug Abuse Council (MADAC) to have successfully graduated from the community-based rehabilitation program from 2018 to the present. The subject participants were men and women of legal age and married, with a live-in partner and someone with a close relationship. Five of these 142 subject participants participated in the in-depth interview and five in the focus-group discussion.

The 142 drug surrenderers were confirmed by Drug Enforcement Agency (PDEA) based on completing fourteen days of community-based rehabilitation programs from 8:00-5:00 pm in the barangay Imbatug and Municipal Training of Baungon Bukidnon by the Municipal Anti-Drug Abuse Council (MADAC) under the community-based rehabilitation program of the Local Government Unit (LGU) of Baungon, Bukidnon.

In this study, the sample was drawn using simple random sampling, in which each member of the population had an equal chance of being chosen. The goal of a simple random sample is to pick people who are common in the whole population. Ababa et al. (2007) say systematic sampling is a slight change from simple random sampling.

In the case of drug surrenderers, the researcher sent a letter to the Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency (PDEA), Local Government Unit, and Barangay to request the list of the drug surrenderers who graduated from the community-based rehabilitation program in 2018. Based on the conversation with the Barangay Captain and the researcher, it was also clear that the data released was confidential

to protect the privacy and safety of the drug surrenderers. Most of the participants were employed, with only one who had membership in a civic organization.

Based on the records of the Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency (PDEA) Regional Office X, 225 drug surrenderers from 10 barangays of Baungon Bukidnon have graduated from the community-based rehabilitation program in 2018 and present. Using the Raosoft online sample size calculator with a 5% margin of error, the suggested sample size is 142 drug surrenderers. The researcher also ensured that the participation of the five drug surrenderers during the in-depth interview and five drug surrenderers in the focus group discussion would be based on their willingness to share their experiences and opinions after they attended the rehabilitation.

Table 1. Socio-Demographic Profile of Subject Participants

<i>Socio-Demographic Profile</i>	
Participant 1	Allan, a 33-year-old, is in a romantic relationship and stays with his parents and two siblings. He is a Roman Catholic who worked as a cultural technician with a degree but no organization. Whenever he needed comfort, her girlfriend was always on his side.
Participant 2	Arvin is a 46-year-old married man who lives with his spouse, two children, and parents. He is a Roman Catholic and a government worker who finished a bachelor's degree. He was not involved with organizations because he had his wife to turn to when he had problems.
Participant 3	Francis is a 29-year-old man with a live-in partner relationship status. He is a Roman Catholic who is now undergoing military training. He graduated from college with a civic organization and a live-in companion to monitor and support him in times of difficulty.
Participant 4	Ian is a 55-year-old widower who lives by himself in a hut. His occupation was that of a government worker. He is a Roman Catholic with a college diploma who had not joined any organization. He only relied on his godson when he wanted a companion.
Participant 5	Jason is a 24-year-old bachelor student who resides with his aunt. He is a Roman Catholic and enrolled in a Bachelor of Science in Public Administration course. He does not belong to groups and relies on his cousin and aunt to listen to him whenever he faces challenges.
Participant 6	Jerome is a 45-year-old married driver who has three children. He is a Roman Catholic, high school graduate who is not an active member of any organization. When he has a dilemma, he turns to his wife for help.
Participant 7	Leo, is 46 years old married, has four children. His highest level of schooling was elementary, and he is a Christian who did not belong to any group. His only companion is his wife.
Participant 8	Maria is a 40-year-old single woman who lives with her family of three. She belong to the United Church of Christ in the Philippines. Her income come from selling food on the street. She attained a high school diploma as her highest level of education. She does not belong to any organization and has her sister support her in times of difficulty.
Participant 9	Mark is a 38-year-old, married, and who lives with his wife and one child. He is a Roman Catholic and a government employee. His highest level of education was vocational or technical schooling. He does not belong to any group and has only his wife to confide in when he has concerns.
Participant 10	Peter, a 37-year-old bachelor, resides with his father and is a Roman Catholic. He was a security guard. His highest level of education was vocational or technical training. He does not belong to any group, and his father is his only companion.

The summary of the socio-demographic profile of drug surrenderers described the profiles of ten participants who underwent in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. Four of the participants are married, three of them are single, one is widowed, one is single, and one has romantic relationship status. The age range by generation belonged to Millennials and Gen X. Specifically, they are Roman Catholic, and there is only one United Church of Christ member in the Philippines. A bachelor's degree was the common highest educational attainment, while two of them have a high school diploma, one has an elementary education, one has vocational training, and one is currently studying.

Instrument

The study employed a research instrument adopted by Zimet (2016). The instrument has three original dimensions: friend, significant other, and family (emotional support). All the items in the questionnaire were kept the same because they fit the present study. The questionnaire has two parts. Part I of the questionnaire is about the socio-demographic profile. Part II is composed of questions regarding perceived social support. Part II of the questionnaire consists of items 6, 7, 9, & 12 for friends, items 1, 2, 5, & 10 are intended for the significant other, and statements 3, 4, 8, & 11 are for family. The researcher sought the approval of the author of the instrument for its utilization, which he granted via email.

There was another instrument used that was intended for the in-depth interview and focus group discussion. The questionnaire was semi-structured with questions about the effects of social support on the drug surrenderers during their recovery process, for both emotional and instrumental support. The results of the in-depth interview and the focus group discussions helped to back up and expand on the study's quantitative results.

Administration of the Instrument

The Municipal Anti-Drug Abuse Council (MADAC) and a social worker reviewed the research instruments used in the study during the survey, in-depth interviews, and focus group discussions. Before beginning the research process, the researcher asked permission

from the academic administrators at Bukidnon State University, including the thesis advisor, program coordinator, department program coordinator, and college dean. After the research panel approved the research proposal, the researcher had to follow a protocol set by the Bukidnon State University Research Ethics Committee (BuKSU-REC) review board.

Right after the review of the research protocol, the researcher was given a decision letter from the BuKSU-REC. The decision letter indicated that the study had been approved, allowing the researcher to proceed. A permit to collect data was requested from the Local Government Unit of Baungon Bukidnon's Municipal Anti-Drug Abuse Council (MADAC) and Municipal Social Welfare and Development (MSWD). In addition, the researcher met the subject participants to distribute the printed survey questionnaire with the attached informed consent of the participants as scheduled by the barangay captain, who accompanied the researcher together with one representative of the Municipal Anti-Drug Abuse Council and one social worker from the Municipal Social Welfare and Development (MSWD) Baungon, Bukidnon.

In the in-depth interviews and focus group discussion, the researcher conducted proper protocol for participants to provide basic information about the study. During the briefing process, the subject participants were informed about the researcher's background, including the study's objectives and purpose. Further, the process and flow of the in-depth and focus group discussion were explained to them.

Before the conduct of the in-depth interview and focus group discussion, the researcher informed and asked permission from participants to audio-record their responses, which lasted from forty-five minutes to one hour. The participants were asked about the social support they received from their friends, significant other, friends, barangay, local government unit, and membership in the organization after graduating from the community-based rehabilitation program in 2018.

In addition, the researcher allotted five (5) minutes for briefing and debriefing per participant. The researcher also clarified that the audio-recorded interview would undergo transcription and be kept confidential. The researcher used a corresponding number for every participant to protect the participants' privacy and anonymity. All the participant's involvement in the research process was voluntary. Suppose a participant refuses to continue the interview and focus group discussion and does not wish to answer any questions. In that case, he/she can withdraw his/her consent and discontinue anytime.

When a participant exhibits behaviors suggestive that the discussion/interview is too stressful, such as uncontrolled crying, shaking, signs of relapse, and emotional outbursts during the in-depth and focus group discussion, the researcher immediately stops the interview and discussion. The condition of the participants was assessed with the help of the social worker. If the subject participant feels able to carry on or continue, then the researcher will resume the interview and focus group discussion. To secure the participants' health and safety during the study, the researcher provided facemasks, face shields, and alcohol to secure them from possible contamination by the virus before the interview. The subject participants' in-depth interviews and focus group discussions were conducted inside the barangay office. The researcher sent a letter for approval to utilize the barangay office as a venue.

The researcher scheduled the in-depth interview and focus group discussion every weekend based on the availability of the drug surrenderers. In order to secure also the safety of the researcher, research assistant, and social worker, they wore facemasks, and face shields, to avoid possible transmission of the virus and observed the one-meter social distance. The social worker's presence was needed to ensure that the participation of the subject participants would not be coerced and forced. The researcher re-echoed the purpose of the study and the goal of the research and thanked them for participating in the study.

Further, if the participants do not allow it, all information gathered is removed and deleted permanently. The researcher also emphasized that their participation has remuneration whether they agreed or not to have their data used in this study.

Lastly, all personnel and persons involved in the study conducted disinfected themselves to avoid possible risks of virus contamination. The researcher made sure to sanitize the materials used in the interview. The researcher acknowledged her responsibility in ensuring the participants' health security in conducting the research and guaranteeing their utmost benefit to this study. After the data gathering, the researcher listened to the recording and made notes. To develop a holistic sense of the study, the researcher repeatedly listened to the audio recording of the interview to become familiar with the words of the interviewee/informant.

Scoring Procedures

The scoring procedure was based on the responses provided by the respondents to the survey questionnaire. The 7-point Likert scale was used in the study's Table 1 scoring procedure, which was based on the original scoring procedure of the questionnaire of Zimet (2016). The questionnaire's items 1–25 were graded on a 1–7 scale, with 1=very strongly disagree, 2=strongly disagree, 3=mildly disagree, 4=neutral, 5=mildly agree, 6=strongly agree, and 7=very strongly agree.

Table 2. 7-Point Likert Scale on Level of Perceived Social Support

Scale	Range	Qualitative Description	Qualifying Statements
7	6.16-7.00	very strongly agree	The drug surrenderers have very high level of social support.
6	5.30-6.15	strongly agree	The drug surrenderers have high level of social support.
5	4.44-5.29	mildly agree	The drug surrenderers have mildly high level of social support.

4	3.58-4.43	Neutral	The drug surrenderers have neither high nor low level of social support.
3	2.72-3.57	mildly disagree	The drug surrenderers have mildly low level of social support.
2	1.86-2.71	strongly disagree	The drug surrenderers have low level of social support.
1	1.00-1.85	very strongly disagree	The drug surrenderers have very low level of social support.

Data Analysis

For this study, statistical methods were used to treat and analyze the answers of the respondents in order to get accurate and reliable data. The researcher used SPSS (Statistical Program for Social Services) to do descriptive and inferential statistics.

Yellapu (2018) says that descriptive statistics were used to organize data summaries by showing how variables in a sample or population are related. At the same time, inferential statistics use statistical methods to make assumptions about the relationships between variables. Descriptive statistics, on the other hand, use statistical methods to find relationships between variables (Kuhar, 2010).

The results from the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions were examined and explored to create codes to find categories, patterns, or themes. These results are interpreted to support the quantitative results from the survey questionnaire.

The following statistics were provided to help analyze and interpret the data. The researcher used frequency counts, percentage distribution, mean, standard deviation, Mann-Whitney, and Kruskal-Wallis.

To answer Problem 1, the socio-demographic profile of subject participants' was presented using the frequency counts and percentage distribution. For problem 2, the table was presented and discussed based on the mean and standard deviation to provide analysis and dispersion of the responses on the respondents' perceived social support level from the survey. To answer problems 3 and 5 on the social support of drug surrenderers according to instrumental support from friends, significant other, and family and to explore if social supports affect drug surrenderers' recovery process, the thematic analysis was applied and to identify the significant difference for problem 4, gender and membership in an organization, it was answered through Mann Whitney method. At the same time, age, civil status, and educational attainment were interpreted using the Kruskal-Wallis method.

The Kruskal-Wallis test was used if you have three or more conditions that you want to compare, and each condition was performed by a different group of participants, i.e., you have an independent- measures design with three or more conditions. It tells us if the differences between the groups were so significant that they are unlikely to have occurred by chance (Hole, 2011). According to Nachar (2008), the Mann- Whitney U test is a non-parametric test that can answer the researcher's questions concerning the difference between groups. The Mann-Whitney test compares each observation from the first group with each observation from the second group.

The data analysis for in-depth interviews and focus group discussions was done through thematic analysis. Thematic analysis is a method for describing data, but it also involves interpretation in selecting codes and constructing themes. Thematic analysis was designed to search for joint or shared meanings of the social support received by the drug surrenderers from their friends, significant others, families, barangay, local government unit, and membership in an organization (Kiger & Varpio, 2020).

Ethical Considerations

The participant's responses in the study were secure and confidential. The researcher prepared an agreement per participants that his or her consent was given without force or coercion via the informed consent form. The purpose and objectives of the study were disclosed to the respondents. All the data collected for the study was intended only for academic enrichment.

On Risk. The risk in this study would be limited to health considerations regarding the COVID-19 pandemic but addressed with proper health protocols followed at all costs. The data gathering was done face-to-face following the IATF protocol, in which the participants wore face masks and underwent sanitation. The respondents were divided to control the population size and secure the safety of everyone who participated in the study. During the in-depth interview and focus group discussion, the researcher ensures a conducive and safe interview venue. The interview was scheduled at a time that was convenient for the participants. The researcher was meticulous in protecting their privacy, and the data gathered.

On benefits. If participants decided to participate in this study, they would receive no personal use. No personal gain would result from a respondent's participation in this study. It is believed that this study's findings would aid the Local Government Unit (LGU) under the Municipal Anti-Drug Abuse Council (MADAC) and Municipal Social Welfare and Development (MSWD) in improving and growing their program to deal with drug-related problems in the Municipality of Baugon, Bukidnon.

As to cost and compensation, the researcher considered giving them a token as an appreciation for their participation in the research process.

The time that respondents spent in this study was solely voluntary. Concerning the participant's rights, their participation in this study was entirely voluntary, and they could initially refuse to participate or stop participating if they wanted. Suppose they decide not to take part or leave the study early. In that case, it will not hurt their relationship with the researcher, the municipal anti-drug abuse council staff, the social worker, or the Baugon, Bukidnon local government unit. Nevertheless, all the subject-participant voluntarily and continued to participate in the research.

On confidentiality. Data from the survey questionnaire was kept secret to the extent that laws and regulations allowed and were made available to the public. But the Bukidnon State University Research Ethics Review Committee, which looks over and approves studies involving people, can review and copy the records to check on the quality and the data. All forms may contain private information. To ensure confidentiality to the extent permitted by the Research Ethics Committee, there were measures applied in the study: the data, or the responses of the respondents, from answering the survey questionnaire was stored on a password-protected computer at all times, and the data was kept solely until the study's completion and publication.

Results and Discussion

This section summarized, analyzed, and evaluated the data collected from the respondents and participants. This study employed a mixed-method research approach to collect sufficient data, which includes surveys, in-depth interviews, and focus group discussions.

The objectives of the study were: a) determining the socio-demographic profile of the respondents; b) identifying the level of perceived social support of drug surrenderers' friends, significant other, and family; c) describing the instrumental support of barangay, local government unit, and membership in an organization of drug surrenderers; d) analyzing the significant difference between drug surrenderers' perceived social support based on their age, civil status, educational attainment, gender, and membership in an organization and; e) exploring the social support that affects the recovery process of drug surrenderers.

This chapter presents the discussion of the statement of problem number one about the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents. Problem numbers two and four are shown using tables supported by the responses from in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. The statement of problem numbers three and five is presented using thematic analysis.

Statement of the Problem # 1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents?

The table displayed the distribution of the respondents based on age, number of children, gender, civil status, religion, educational attainment, occupation, involvement in an organization, family size, and confinement with family members.

Table 3. *Socio-demographic Data of Community Based-Rehabilitation Program Drug Surrenderers*

<i>Socio-demographic characteristics</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Age		
20-29 years old	38	26.8
30-39 years old	66	46.5
40-49 years old	34	23.9
> 50 years old	4	2.8
Number of Children		
No child	8	5.6
1-2 children	44	31.0
3-4 children	55	38.7
>5 children	35	24.6
Sex		
Male	139	97.9
Female	3	2.1
Civil Status		
Married	100	70.4
Live-in partner	25	17.6
With close relationship	17	12.0
Religion		
Catholic	127	89.4
Non-Catholic	15	10.6
Educational Attainment		
Some elementary level	49	34.5
Some high school level	15	10.6
High School graduate	51	35.9
Vocational	14	9.9
Bachelor's degree	13	9.2
Occupation		
Unemployed	15	0.6
Laborer/Welder/Driver/Vendor/SG	103	72.2
HR/Clerk/Agri-tech/Estimator	5	3.5
Government Employee	8	5.6
Farmer	11	7.7
Membership to an Organization		
No	127	89.4
Yes	15	10.6

Family Size		
< 3 members	16	11.3
4-5 members	53	37.3
6-7 members	41	28.9
>8 members	32	22.5
Confinement to Relatives		
Yes	60	42.3
No	82	57.7

According to the data presented, most respondents were aged 30 to 39. This data is accurate for drug surrenderers in Baungon because aged 30 to 39-year-old belong to the generation of millennials and Gen X. Based on the survey conducted by the National Statistics Office (2019), a total of 6.9% of those 18-59 years old have tried taking dangerous drugs/ substances.

Added by Active Marketing (2020), the millennial generation (those born between 1984 and 1993) is more disillusioned than prior generations, where today's youth suffer more. Further, Silvermist Recovery (2021) suggested that millennials' dependency on technology may raise their likelihood of having a substance use disorder. Taking drugs was the only efficient escape available for them (Alavi et al., 2012).

Based on the data and sources cited above, the millennials and Gen X were most likely victims of drug-related problems because they have encountered numerous obstacles, ranging from an uncertain career path and a declining economy to worrying about global warming and the sustainability of their current lifestyle. Further, during this stage, most of the respondents were socially active in the community, where most were working individuals with a network of people like co-workers and friends, making them vulnerable to drug addiction.

In terms of marital status, they were predominantly married. Similar to the survey conducted by the Dangerous Drug (2020), about fifty-three percent (53.03%) are single, twenty-five percent (24.74%) are married, seventeen percent (17.43%) have live-in partners, and the remaining five percent (4.8%) are widows or widowers, separated, divorced, or annulled. This claim was explained by the study conducted by Budirahayu &

Fisip (2020) that child marriage is an expression of society's symptoms and social structure. Supported by Hanum & Tukiman (2015), parents use their situation to escape their obligation to their children. Added to Maghsoudi et al. (2019), when married women turned drug addicts, they may experience emotional burdens, financial constraints, relationship conflicts, and multiple responsibilities.

One factor explaining why most of them were married was that the research locale was considered a rural area composed of fewer people who were familiar with each other. Knowingly, individuals living in this kind of community have different cultural practices. Generally, small groups have homogenous culture compared to big groups. As for them, they married early because of poverty, and access to education was unavailable, which explained why many of them were married.

In terms of the number of children, the respondents have an average of three to four children and a family size of four to five members. This result was supported by the study of Lodhi et al. (2021), that out of 43 responders surveyed, 33 were from a nuclear family with three to four family members.

According to Gozum (2021), Filipinos value the family in the Philippines because tradition and history have taught them that it is sacred. Canete (2021) states that this demonstrates that the Filipino family's faith contributed to their high regard for the sanctity of family life, and the Catholic Church only adhered to the traditional "safe period" than the modern family planning methods. Added to Ignaciuk & Kelly (2020), using artificial birth control could lead to extramarital affairs and a significant decline in moral standards.

Since the majority of the respondents in the study are Roman Catholics, they believe that children are blessings and, therefore, have a large family. In addition, the Roman Catholic church opposes modern family planning for the church to promote pro-life. Filipinos have long been known for their strong family values and the culture of extended families. In terms of gender, there were more male than female drug users.

According to the Dangerous Drug Board (2021), most men in the Philippines take drugs at a rate of 90.47%, compared to 8.83% of women. Moreover, gender differences in using drugs were socially determined roles that vary across cultures and over time (Fonseca et al., 2021). For instance, the concept of machismo as related to drug addiction is viewed negatively. This unfavorable impression can cause a power struggle between men and women, leading to domestic violence in partnerships and families, especially in cases of drug addiction (Ceballos & Middleton, 2013).

Most drug surrenderers in the study were men, and the population of women was limited to men. Nonetheless, it was also confirmed that men are susceptible to addiction. In the Filipino setting, men are viewed as vital; hence, a guy's drug addiction was considered natural because it was viewed as a sign of becoming a strong and true man. In addition, males are expected to provide for their families, which makes them more visible outside the home and a significant risk factor for drug addiction.

In terms of religion, Roman Catholicism was the most common religion of the respondents. This indicates that Roman Catholicism was still the preferred faith of most drug surrenderers when this study was conducted. As of 2020, there are more than 108,667,043

households in the Philippines (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2023). The introduction of Roman Catholicism in the Philippines can be attributed to the Spanish colonial period, specifically to the arrival of the Portuguese explorer Ferdinand Magellan in 1521 (Cruz, 1995).

Surprisingly, most drug surrenderers have an average highest educational attainment as a high school graduate, followed by those who had finished elementary school. Very few of them had a bachelor's degree.

As observed by Gomes de Matos et al. (2021), individuals with lower levels of education were at a higher risk for drug use and problem drug use. Further, according to the article by Moussawi et al. (2017), there is a relationship between education and drug addiction, suggesting that higher levels of education may protect against drug addiction by increasing knowledge, critical thinking skills, and access to resources. In general, according to Mahfudin & Waqi'ah (2016), rural areas have a relatively low level of education, which influences their way of thinking.

The Bukidnon State University External Studies Center in Baungon was opened in 2005. Unfortunately, the external study center stopped enrolling first-year students in 2015. In 2018 it was re-opened as a Satellite campus and provided free tuition to the students. The alteration above in the educational system of the municipality has significantly affected the level of education of drug surrenderers, which explains why most respondents were only high school graduates.

In terms of occupation, the data also revealed that most of the respondents belonged to low-skilled workers like laborers, welders, drivers, vendors, and security guards, which were the most popular occupation. These working drug surrenderers include government employees, human resource professionals, clerks, agri-tech specialists, estimators, and farmers. Some respondents were unemployed while the research was being conducted.

The National Institute on Drug Abuse (2018) has shown that there is a correlation between low-skilled work and drug addiction. Individuals whose occupation is construction, food service, and transportation have higher rates of drug use than those in other occupations (National Institute on Drug Abuse, 2015). As supported by Mennis et al. (2016), low-skilled workers are more likely to use drugs than high-skilled workers due to lower income, less access to healthcare, and less social support. Additionally, low-skilled workers are more likely to experience job-related stress, which can lead to drug use as a coping mechanism (Babor et al., 2010).

Drug addiction may be more prevalent among low-skilled workers because their jobs often involve physically demanding work or long hours, leading to stress and fatigue. Additionally, low-skilled workers may have limited access to education or job opportunities, leading to hopelessness and despair. These factors can make individuals more susceptible to turning to drugs to cope with their difficulties.

In terms of involvement in an organization, unfortunately, most of the respondents in the study do not belong to or participate in any organization. As cited by the National Institute on Drug Abuse (2021), drug addiction can lead to social isolation and withdrawal in the community. Society can stigmatize drug addiction, and individuals may feel ashamed or unwelcome in community settings. These underlying issues can make it difficult for individuals to connect with others and participate in community or religious activities (Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration, 2018).

Many people who struggle with addiction feel embarrassed or ashamed about their situation. Most of them have other priorities; aside from that, they may lack resources and may not have the resources or support they need to participate in other activities. It is important to remember that addiction is a complex issue, and people struggling with it may face various challenges that make it difficult for them to engage in other activities.

Lastly, in terms of relative confinement majority of them rely on family members during difficult times. The study by Opeyemi (2018) proved that individuals in drug rehabilitation with strong family support are more likely to rely on their family during difficult times. Added by Kuntz & Rotgers (2010), family involvement can improve treatment outcomes by providing support, encouragement, and reinforcing positive behaviors and coping strategies. It was also recommended by National Institute on Drug Abuse (2018) that treatment programs must need to involve family members as possible.

By analyzing the socio-demographic profile of the respondents, we can better understand the needs, preferences, and challenges of different groups of people and develop targeted interventions and policies that address their specific needs, especially in drug addiction.

Statement of the Problem # 2. What is the level of Perceived Social Support of Drug Surrenderers in terms of: Micro-Level Social Support (Emotional Support) friends, significant other, and family?

Table 4. Level of Perceived Micro-Level (Emotional Support) Social Support of Drug Surrenderers

	X	Sd	Qualitative Description	
1. My family is willing to help me make decisions.	6.41	0.78	Very Agree Strongly	The drug surrenderers have very high level of social support.
2. I can talk about my problems with my family.	6.36	0.96	Very Agree Strongly	The drug surrenderers have very high level of social support.
3. My family tries to help me.	6.29	0.95	Very Agree Strongly	The drug surrenderers have very high level of social support.
4. I have a special person who is a real source of comfort	6.29	0.87	Very Agree Strongly	The drug surrenderers have very high level

to me.					of social support.
5. There is a special person in my life who cares about my feelings	6.24	0.90	Very Agree	Strongly	The drug surrenderees have very high level of social support.
6. I get the emotional help and support I need from my family.	6.19	1.18	Very Agree	Strongly	The drug surrenderees have very high level of social support.
7. I can talk about my problem with my friends.	6.19	0.97	Very Agree	Strongly	The drug surrenderees have very high level of social support.
8. There is a special person with whom I can share joys and sorrows.	6.09	1.09	Strongly Agree		The drug surrenderees have high level of social support.
9. My friends really try to help me.	6.05	0.98	Strongly Agree		The drug surrenderees have high level of social support.
10. There is a special person who is around when I am in need.	5.89	1.43	Strongly Agree		The drug surrenderees have high level of social support.
11. I have friends with whom I can share my joys and sorrows.	5.89	0.90	Strongly Agree		The drug surrenderees have high level of social support.
12. I can count on my friends when things go wrong.	5.80	1.20	Strongly Agree		The drug surrenderees have high level of social support.
	Overall Mean	6.14	1.02	Strongly Agree	The drug surrenderees have high level of social support.

Emotional Support

Table 4 presented the micro-level emotional support received by the drug surrenderers from their friends, significant other, and family. The data results in Table 4 were presented from the highest to the lowest mean of social support with in-depth interviews and focus group discussions narrated by the participants.

Friends Support

Based on the data from the survey questionnaire, the result showed that most respondents claimed that they have a very high level of social support from their friends, with the highest mean of 6.36. Particularly about having friends with whom they can talk about their problems, with the highest mean of 6.36. Two participants supported the result from the surveyed questionnaire. Participant # 1 & # 8 shared,

“Magkitaay lang me sa akoang barkada pero naa gud barkada nga muhanganat saimoha ug kaon mutagad gud. Unya kung naa mga birthday inbitaron ko, diha na dayun mi mag bonding ug istorya-istorya kung unsa na amoang kahintang sa kinabuhi (My friends and I see each other during social events such as birthdays. I have friends who really would take their time to bond with me and make updates on our lives).”

Interpersonal gatherings such as birthdays were the only avenue for the participant to unite with her friends; that way, she could communicate and share her problems.

Another survey result showed that most of the subject participants have high social support regarding friends who help them, with a mean score of 6.05. This result was attested by Participant # 3, a 29-year-old drug surrenderer who received help from his friends via words of encouragement. He confirmed,

“Akoa mga barkada hatagan ko nila ug advice nga magpadayun ko sa pag bag-o kay limpiyo nako karun. Pwede nako makipaghalubilo nako sa lain tao kay dili naman ko adik (My friends will give me advice that I should continue to change because I am clean now. I can socialize with other people because I am not an addict anymore).”

On the other hand, acceptance from his friends was the other help experienced by Participant # 8 and Participant # 5 after treatment. Taken from the in-depth interview and focus group discussion, participant # 8 explained how her friends never hesitated to accept her again and never doubted her even after undergoing the community-based rehabilitation program. She shared,

“Istoryahon gihapon ko sa ako mga barkada nako bisan pa nakabalo sila nga nag gikan ko sa CBRP. Wala nabag-o ila pag tagad sa ako ug wala sad ko nila likaye (My friends still talk to me even though they knew that I came from CBRP. They didn't change and they didn't avoid me either).” This scenario was also undergone by participant # 5 by saying that, “Gidawat gyapon ko sa ako mga barkada pag human nakog recover (My friends still accepted me after I recovered).”

Social support from friends is a crucial factor in drug rehabilitation programs (Stewart et al., 2017). It provides motivation, encouragement, and reinforcement for positive behavior change (Harris & Edlund, 2005), and it helps individuals develop new social networks essential for long-term recovery (Kelly & Yeterian, 2015).

According to Feldstein et al. (2016), social support from friends can provide a sense of belonging and purpose, motivating them to avoid relapse. Additionally, Brooks et al. (2016) suggest that friends can help provide a stable and supportive environment. This type of support can also help individuals to rebuild their social skills, which may have been damaged due to substance abuse (Moyers et al.,

2016). Torrecillas et al. (2015) argued that friends' social support refers to a concept in which a drug addict shares problems with close friends to find harmonious solutions. Friends' support is a concept that involves drug addicts sharing their problems with their close friends.

The support of the friends includes providing advice and sharing experiences on how to deal with drug addiction. Reif et al. (2014) found that effective treatment and rehabilitation sometimes rely on the quality of a patient's interpersonal relationships. The support of a compassionate friend is a form of healing for them.

Lastly, Pedrosa et al. (2020) added that friends are not only considered a source of psychological and physical protection; they also provide much-needed social support. If a patient is having trouble with therapy, his or her friends can be a great source of support; they play a part in the rehabilitation from a disease or addiction.

For several reasons, friends might continue to accept drug surrenderers who have undergone a community-based rehabilitation program. A friend may have a deep empathy and understanding toward the drug surrenderers' struggles with drug addiction. They have a strong personal connection and shared histories that create a bond between friends that transcends the challenges of addiction. Being known by friends for a long time means they are willing to stand by their friends despite their past struggles, focusing on the positive aspects of their relationship. Others firmly believe in giving second chances to people who have made mistakes.

In addition, friends who have witnessed their loved one's commitment to change during the rehabilitation program may develop a sense of trust in their friend's efforts. They may believe their friend is genuinely motivated to stay drug-free and willing to offer ongoing support. Aside from that, friends can play a vital role in providing social support and accountability to individuals in recovery. By accepting their friend post-rehabilitation, they may create an environment that fosters positive change and discourages relapse. It is important to note that continued support from friends alone may not be sufficient for a successful recovery. Professional help, ongoing treatment, and a supportive community are crucial to maintaining sobriety.

Social support from friends is essential for a successful recovery. A supportive network of friends can provide emotional support and encouragement during difficult times. This is important to people who may have lost contact with family members or do not have a supportive home environment. Friends can also serve as positive role models and sources of inspiration. Social support from friends is essential to the recovery process from drug addiction. It can provide emotional, practical, and motivational support to help individuals overcome addiction challenges and build a fulfilling life in recovery.

Significant Other

The data also revealed that statistically, subject participants have a very high level of social support from their significant other because there is a particular person who is a natural source of comfort to them, with the highest mean of 6.29. There is also a particular person who cares about their feelings.

During the in-depth interview and focus group discussion, two participants claimed they received emotional comfort from their wives. Participant # 9, a 38-year-old drug surrenderer, explained how his wife became a source of comfort by advising him about legal matters that benefit him regarding his operational issues. He shared,

“Kung sa akong wife always mana siya naa ga support sa akong advice pod. So siguro ang pinaka supportive jud siya mismo sa pag advice kabahin sa akong problema. Mostly man sa akong problema kay sa trabaho hilabina about sa legal nga mga pamaagi labing kaso-kaso kay syempre naa siya sa PNP so mas more knowledgeable siya about sa legal so siya permente makasabot 100%. Kung kinahanglan ko ug advice naa jud siya permi (When it comes to my wife, she always supports me and gives me advice. She is the most supportive in giving advice about my problem. Most of my problems is about work especially about legal matters especially of course she is in the PNP, so she is more knowledgeable about the legal process so she always understands 100%. If I need advice, she is always there).”

Moreover, participant # 2, who is 46-year-old shared what his wife did to make him stop using drugs.

“Ang suport na gihimo sa akong misis nga after ko pag CBRP dako kay naay panahon nga nag-ingon siya nga kung dili ko mag undang ipadakop ko niya sa mga pulis. Nakatabang man gud siya sa ako kay ang effect dayun ato kay dili na nako ipa anhi ako barkada sa balay kay basin ako wife mag sumbong (My wife's support after I went to CBRP was great because there was a time when she said that if I didn't stop, she would have the police arrest me. She really helped me because the effect is that I no longer invite my friends to the house because my wife might file a complaint).”

This kind of emotional guidance has become a great help in controlling him. Participant # 3, who is 29, year old-drug surrenderer narrated how his live-in partner provided emotional monitoring on him,

“Kada adlaw akong partner nga toa sa abroad iya gud ko ikonsulta kung unsa akong gibuhad, nagkaon naba ko, unsa akong gibuhad karun nga adlaw always ko niya gina monitor. Kung uban ko sa mga barkada iya ko permente pasidad-an nga kung mag inom ibutang lang sa tiyan ug naa limitasyon kay init mi sa mata sa mga pulis ug dili maapil sa kagubot (Every day my partner who is abroad monitors me about what I'm doing, whether I'm eating, what I'm doing today, she always monitors me. When I'm with friends, he always warns me that when I drink, I only put it on my stomach and there is a limit because we are hot in the eyes of the police and we should not

get involved in any chaos).”

The location of Francis's live-in partner is not an obstacle to providing his partner with the emotional support he needs. Aside from the emotional support received from wives and live-in partners, participant # 4 and Participant # 5 also felt emotional guidance from their godson and cousin. For instance, participant # 4, aged 55, described how his godson comforted him through words of affirmation by saying,

“Positive ang mga tambag nga gihatag sa akong godson sa akoa nga dili najud ko mag gamit usab sa drugs kay makadaot na. Karun permente rami mag istorya and mag exchange ug ideas. Usahay Mag, his got rami about sa current events, mga sakyanan, and government issues (The advice that my godson gave me was that I should not use drugs because they are harmful. Now we always talk and exchange ideas. Sometimes we talk about current events, cars, and government issues).”

His godson was also the only one who cared about his feelings by sharing and listening to him when they were conversing. The cousin also of Participant # 5 gave emotional guidance to him and boosted his emotional condition by sharing positive things.

“Akoang ig-agaw gina advisan ko na dili na mag gamit ug drugs nga mag bag- o na kay kabalo nako unsay sayup ug maayo. Wala gud nag ingon ug mga negative nga istorya akong ig-agaw sa ako wala pod ko niya gikaminusan nga pag human sa pag recover iya noon ko gi enourage nga dili na mag gamit sa drug utro (My cousin is guiding me not to use drugs anymore because I know what is wrong and what is good. My cousin never said any negative stories about me nor did he underestimate me after recovering, instead he encouraged me not to use drugs again).”

Research has shown that social support plays a vital role in recovery (Laudet, Morgen, & White, 2006). According to Glassman (2013), support from significant other at treatment entry has been associated with lower drug use. As Laudet et al. (2006) supported, social support from a significant other can help individuals in recovery feel less isolated and more motivated to stay sober. Thus, having a supportive partner invested in the individual's recovery can help create a sense of accountability and responsibility (Kelly et al., 2011).

The significant other may have a deep emotional connection and love for their partner. Despite the challenges and difficulties of drug addiction and rehabilitation, they choose to stand by their partner because of their emotional bond. They believe in the potential for change and will support their partner's recovery journey.

A partner can also provide emotional support by being a sounding board for their struggles, offering encouragement and positive reinforcement, and being a source of comfort during difficult times. Therefore, social support from a significant other is a critical component of the recovery process from drug addiction. A supportive partner can provide emotional and practical support, improving the chances of successful recovery and reducing the risk of relapse. A significant other can also offer practical support, such as helping you stay accountable for your actions, reminding you to attend meetings or therapy sessions, and providing a safe and stable home environment.

Family Support

Family support significantly contributed to drug surrenderers' recovery, as suggested by the survey questionnaire results on the level of perceived emotional support of drug surrenderers in terms of family support. Drug surrenderers have a very high level of social support because their families are willing to help them make decisions with the highest mean score, and they can talk about their problems with their families.

Participant # 9 shared how his parents help him make decisions through guidance. He emphasized that they had a significant part in convincing him to join the community-based rehabilitation program, which resulted in a helpful result.

“Akoang ginikanan gyud ang nakatabang sa akoang pag recover kay sila ang nagpa sulod sa ako sa programa. Lahi man gud ni kung ang ginikanan na ang mag istorya kay kinasing-kasing permente. Ang istorya sa ginikanan kumoton atong kasing kasing mao nakadecide nako nga mag give up nako mao 100% ang tambag sa ginikanan makaayo para maulian sa drugs (My parents really helped me recover because they were the ones who put me in the program. It's completely different when the parents are the ones who talk because it's always heart-to-heart. The story of the parents is so heart breaking that I decided to give up because 100% the advice of the parents is good for recovering from drugs).”

Another participant also claimed that his family supported him through words of encouragement. Participant # 3 claimed,

“Sa akong pamilya dako gyapon kaayo silag natabang sa akoa. Kanang ila ko istoryahan nga kabalo nako unsay maayo ug dili maayo. Dapat kuno ipakita nako sa mga tao nga naa koy maabot sa akong kinabuhi. Akong pamilya naghatag gud love sa akoa (My family, helped me a lot. They will tell me that I know what is good and what is not good. I should show people that I have something to achieve in my life. My family really loves me).”

This support was also experienced by Participant # 2 and Participant # 4. Participant # 2, for instance, was warned by his parents about the unexpected things that might happen to him if he will not stop using drugs.

“Akong ginikanan kay permente ko nila advisan nga dili na mag apil-apil sa pag gamit sa drugs kay basin muabot ang panahon nga naay daotan nga mahitabo sa akoa (My parents always advice me not to get involved in the use of drugs because the time might come

when something bad will happen to me).”

Participant # 2, on the other hand, is under surveillance by his parents to ensure he will not relapse. He shared,

“Sa akong pamilya daghan ilang advice sa akong mga muhungan sila nga dili nako mag utro sa pag gamit ug drugs. Ilaha nako gabantayan para dili na mubalik paggamit sa drugs hilabina if makita ko nila mag uban sa akong barkada ilaha ko badlungon nga basin nag gamit napod ko drugs (In my family, they give me a lot of advice that they tell me not to use drugs. They will watch me so that I don't go back to using drugs, especially if they see me with my friends, they will scold me that I might be using drugs).”

Participant # 5 shared that when he started attending the after-care session, his relationship with his aunt and mother improved, allowing him to share his problems without fear and shame freely. He shared,

“Pagsugod nako ug after-care session naay kausaban nga akong nabantayan sa akong kaugalingon pila ka months kay istoryahon na nako ako mama. Aside ana nabalik akong maayo nga relasyon sa akong tita dati. Pag recover nako maka share nako sa akong problema sa akong tita ug mama. Kay sauna man gud ako lang tago-tagoan ako nga problema (When I started attending the after-care session, I noticed a change in myself, for a few months because I could freely talk to my mother. Aside from that, my good relationship with my aunt has returned. I can share my problem with my aunt and mom when I recovered, because before I keep my problems to myself).”

The Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration (2015) proposed that social support from family members can improve treatment outcomes and reduce the risk of relapse. Based on the results of the study conducted by Rachman et al. (2020), 83.9% of the respondents received positive social support. As supported by the interview conducted by Syazrah Mohd Ghazali et al. (2017), most of the participants agreed that family support is essential. As suggested by Nguyen et al. (2016), the drug surrenderers who receive more help from their families showed a more positive attitude toward drug treatment.

Filipino families strongly emphasize the importance of family bonds and solidarity. By encouraging their family members to participate in rehabilitation programs, they provide a crucial support system during recovery. Drug addiction is often associated with stigma and social exclusion in many societies, including the Philippines. By supporting their loved ones' participation in rehabilitation programs, family members aim to reduce the stigma surrounding addiction. They understand that community-based rehabilitation programs can help reintegrate individuals into society, improve their overall well-being, and provide opportunities for reintegration.

On the other hand, Filipino culture is deeply rooted in collectivism, where the needs and well-being of drug surrenderers are prioritized over individual desires. It also fosters a sense of social responsibility and solidarity among family members as they actively participate in the recovery and reintegration process. In addition, Filipino families often have a strong belief in the capacity for personal transformation and change. By supporting their loved ones' involvement in community-based rehabilitation programs, they express optimism and hope for a successful recovery.

Thus, social support from family is important for a successful recovery process. A family member can help create a safe and supportive home environment that promotes sobriety. By removing triggers and temptations from the home, family members can help reduce the risk of relapse. They can also help the person establish healthy habits and routines that support recovery, such as regular exercise, healthy eating, and a consistent sleep schedule.

Statement of the Problem # 3. What are the Social Support received by Drug Surrenderers in terms of: Macro Social Support (Instrumental Support) from barangay or lgu and membership in organization?

Instrumental Support

This part presents the drug surrenderers' instrumental support of the community-based rehabilitation program. The responses came from the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions with the five participants. They talked about the services and programs they received from the barangay, the local government unit, and their membership in an organization. These government institutions and civic organizations have helped them in their healing. Pseudonyms were used to hide their identities and ensure the confidentiality of their accounts.

Barangay and Local Government Unit Support

One important theme that appeared in the study is the instrumental support from the barangay and local government unit. This support is the programs and services experienced and received by the drug surrenderers that have helped fast-track their recovery from drug addiction. This theme has the following sub-themes: (a) After-Care Sessions; (b) Community Service; (c) Financial Support; (d) In-Kind Donations, (e) Livelihood Program; (f) Voluntary Works.

After-Care Session

In the in-depth interview and focus group discussion, the participants claimed that the barangay and local government units conducted the after-care sessions right after the community-based rehabilitation program. These consist of meetings, monitoring, and drug test. The four participants shared the services they experienced while recovering from drug addiction.

“Ang una nga gihatag nga support sa amoa kay ang aftercare dayun nag drug test me every month human sa CBRP ang barangay wala

nag kulang sa pagpahinumdum sa amoa. Ang kapitan nangusog na dili mugamit sa droga para drug free na ang Baungon (The first support given to us was aftercare, followed by the drug test every month after the CBRP. The barangay did not fail to remind us. The captain insisted that we should not use drugs again so that Baungon would be drug-free)” participant # 1 said.

The barangay becomes responsive during the after-care session especially conducting drug tests. They make sure that no one will relapse. The barangay Captain also shows concern for the drug surrenderers by discouraging them from using drugs. One participant mentioned how monitoring, meeting, and drug tests influenced his healing because the services allowed them to assess and observe their day-to-day activities to improve their condition. He said

“One thing nga nakatabang ang barangay sa amoa is kini ang monitoring kada bulan. Unya mag patawag sad meeting tapos amoa sila iupdate kung unsa amoang gipangbuhat kada adlaw tapos mag conduct sila ug drug test sa amoa (One thing that the barangay has helped us with is the monthly monitoring. They call us for a meeting, and we will update them on what we are doing every day, and then they will conduct a drug test on us)” said, participant # 9.

These statements were also factual for the two participants that after-care sessions allowed them to express the change of behavior they observed in themselves, whether positive or negative while undergoing monitoring. Participant # 7 said,

“Among after-care kay naay meeting kada Friday. Diha dayun nga time mag voice out sa mga pag bag-o nga among nabantayan sa amoang kaugalingon, labina kung nakabuhay bami ug maayo o daotan (Our after-care is a meeting every Friday. At that time, we will voice out the changes we have observed in ourselves, especially if we have done something good or bad).”

Similar to Participant # 7, participant # 8, a 40-year-old drug surrenderer, has also had the same experience, that the barangay became a great help for her to heal from addiction. She said

“Para sa akua ang tabang gud sa barangay dako ug tabang sa akua para maulian ko. Hilabina ilang ginabuhay nga pag monitor sa amoa kung naay pag bag-o sa among mga lihok. Kay si kapitan nag tabang para maulian ko. Kutob sa mga drug addict nga nag surrender naulian gud kay ipa under monitoring sa barangay (For me, the help of the barangay is tremendous and helped me recover. They monitor us for any change in our actions because the barangay captain helped me to be healed. The drug addicts who gave up have improved now that the barangay monitored them).”

Research shows that after-care programs can reduce symptoms of depression and anxiety, improve self-esteem, and enhance the overall quality of life (Lash et al., 2010). Added by Kelly, et., al. (2011) agree that after-care programs can help individuals feel less isolated and more supported. As described by Precursors, Chemicals, and Issuances (2014), the aft, care, and follow-up program helps the client get back into the community. Aside from that random drug tests can be given during the program to look for signs of relapse. Persons Who Used Drugs (PWUDs) who test positive will be referred to a qualified doctor for additional testing and treatment (Department of Health 2017).

The After-care sessions provide a supportive environment where drug surrenderers can interact with peers who have gone through similar experiences. They can receive encouragement, empathy, and understanding by sharing their struggles, successes, and coping strategies, which strengthens their resolve to stay drug-free. Through discussions, education, and guidance from professionals or experienced individuals, drug surrenderers can learn effective coping mechanisms, identify triggers, and develop skills to handle high-risk situations.

Educational components are also included in the after-care session that provides drug surrenderers with information about addiction, its causes, and its consequences. This knowledge helps individuals understand the factors contributing to addiction and empowers them to make informed decisions. Drug surrenderers can also engage in discussions, personal reflection, and goal-setting exercises; they can redefine their values, aspirations, and roles within their families and community.

Addiction often involves social networks that support and perpetuate substance abuse. Through group activities, peer support, and mentoring, individuals can build relationships with others who prioritize sobriety and well-being, reinforcing positive behavioral patterns. Lastly, the after-care sessions provide a platform for drug surrenderers to advocate for themselves and others in recovery. By sharing their stories and experiences, they can raise awareness about the challenges faced by individuals recovering from addiction, reduce stigma, and promote a more compassionate and inclusive society.

The after-care sessions are essential to community-based rehabilitation programs for drug surrenderers. Drug surrenderers receive ongoing support and guidance from trained professionals, such as counselors or therapists, during after-care sessions. It also includes educational programs that provide information about addiction and recovery. Services like after-care sessions and random drug tests are essential to community-based rehabilitation programs for drug surrenderers. They provide ongoing support, education, and guidance to help individuals maintain their sobriety and prevent relapse.

Community Service

Community service as a mandatory service from post-rehabilitation programs for drug surrenderers was one of the sub-themes that appeared from the data. Two categories are identified in this sub-themes: clean-up drive and tree planting. Two participants shared their involvement during the community service. The tree planting and clean-up drive were one of the activities conducted by the

barangay to allow the participants to become socially active in the community. This activity enables them to become a steward of the environment and develop a sense of unity amongst their co-drug surrenderers and the community. Participant # 9 said

“Isa sa mga activities nga among gibuhay gikan sa pag human namo sa program is mag tree planting didto sa Mando. Ang ikaduha kay clean-up drive didto sa ubos sa purok 5 sa barangay. Half day man to tapos sunod semana ang tanom sa kahoy (One of the activities we’re doing after our program was tree planting at Mando. The second was the clean-up drive at the bottom of purok 5 of the barangay. It was half-day and then the planting of trees was on the other week).”

Participant # 2 also said he joined community service in their barangay, where they cleaned a spring. He also claimed that activities like clean-up drives and tree planting were only possible if the barangay sent a letter.

“Naay panahon na mag community service mi. Atong niagi nanlimpiyo mi sa spring ug nag tanom ug kahoy. Kung naay activity sa barangay mag hulat ramig sulat” (There is a time when we do community service. The last time, we cleaned the spring, and planted trees. If there is an activity in the barangay, we will wait for a letter)” he shared.

As part of the rehabilitation program, community works like tree planting and other physical fitness activities are planned for drug surrenderers (Sunstar, 2016). According to Afzal and Hussain (2020), drug surrenderers become more involved when they participate in community service programs. The study conducted by Miller and colleagues (2013) shows that participants who engaged in community service reported higher levels of self-esteem, self-efficacy, and social support than those who did not participate in community service.

Another study by O'Connell and colleagues (2016) found that community service can help individuals in recovery develop new skills and interests, which can lead to new opportunities and a sense of accomplishment. Community service is essential for drug surrenderers in community-based rehabilitation programs because it allows them to give back to their community and make amends for any harm they may have caused due to their drug use. By engaging in community service, they can develop a sense of purpose and accomplishment, which can boost their self-esteem and help them stay motivated in their recovery journey. Additionally, community service can help them build positive relationships with their neighbors and show they are committed to positive changes in their lives.

Community service provides an opportunity for drug surrenderers to reintegrate into society. By engaging in activities alongside other community members, they can regain a sense of belonging and establish positive social connections. It helps them develop a sense of responsibility towards their community. By actively contributing to the welfare and improvement of their neighborhood, they can reestablish a sense of purpose and self-worth.

Participating in community service allows drug surrenderers to align themselves with pro-social norms and values prevalent in their community that involve learning new skills or enhancing existing ones. Through participating in various projects, drug surrenderers can acquire vocational or practical skills to improve their employability once they have completed their recovery process.

The peer support system during community service can be instrumental in their recovery process by sharing stories, offering encouragement, and learning from others who have successfully overcome addiction can foster a sense of hope, motivation, and resilience. The drug surrenderers' involvement in community service demonstrates that individuals in recovery can positively contribute to society, debunking stereotypes and promoting a more compassionate and understanding community environment.

Financial Support

During the interview and focus group, one participant mentioned that he received monetary support from the barangay for being an admin lecturer during the barangay symposium, where he spoke about the advantage and disadvantages of using drugs to high school students.

“Dako kaayo ang natabang ang munisipyo sa akong kay gihimo ko nilag lecturer admin sa barangayan symposium about sa advantage and disadvantage sa pag gamit sa droga sa mga high school students human nako nag graduate CBRP program sa 2018 (The municipality helped me a lot because they made me a lecturer admin in the barangayan symposium about the advantage and disadvantage of drug use among high school students after I graduated from CBRP program in 2018)” participant # 4 said.

According to a study by Banta and colleagues (2019), financial support from the barangay was positively associated with drug surrenderers' access to healthcare services, which, in turn, was associated with improved treatment outcomes. Another study by Caoili and colleagues (2018) found that financial support reported lower levels of financial stress and better mental health outcomes compared to those who did not receive financial support.

Pursuant Section 51 of Act and Memorandum Circular No. 2015-63 of DILG, mandates that the local government unit shall appropriate a substantial portion of their respective annual budgets to assist in or enhance the enforcement of the Act through this regulation (Department of the Interior and Local Government 2018).

Financial support ensures that drug surrenderers have access to their basic needs, such as food, shelter, clothing, and healthcare. By providing financial support, the barangay and local government unit helps alleviate the financial burden on drug surrenderers, allowing them to regain control over their finances and reduce the temptation to resort to substance abuse for economic reasons. It also enables

drug surrenderers to access professional addiction treatment and support services they may not have been able to afford otherwise.

The financial support can be directed towards skill-building programs, vocational training, or educational opportunities for drug surrenderers by providing them with resources to rebuild their lives. It restores their sense of dignity and self-worth, which may have been eroded by addiction, and can help break the cycle of addiction within families and communities.

In-Kind Donations

The in-kind donation was non-monetary support given by the barangay to drug surrenderers. There were some of the participants who were able to receive in-kind donations like food and clothing. One was Participant # 9, who expressed his gratitude to the government as he received food after therapy. He claimed,

“Nagpasalamat ko sa gobyerno nga ilaha ko gitagaan ug pagkaon sa mga times nga naglisod ko. (I thank the government for giving me food when I was struggling)”. This sentiments was also felt by Ian saying, “Nagpasalamt ko sa libre nga pagkaon, sa snack ug sa uniporme nga ilang gihatag (I am thankful for the free food, the snack, and the uniform they gave me).”

According to Manalo and colleagues (2019), drug surrenderers who received in-kind donations support reported lower levels of financial stress and better mental health outcomes. They also have better physical health outcomes compared to those who did not receive in-kind donations support (Natividad and colleagues, 2018)

In-kind donations, such as food, clothing, hygiene items, and household supplies, help meet the basic needs of drug surrenderers. In-kind donations alleviate the economic strain on drug surrenderers by providing necessities they might otherwise struggle to afford. This Act can communicate a message of community support and care for drug surrenderers. By receiving donations, individuals feel valued, recognized, and encouraged, which can enhance their motivation to overcome addiction and maintain their sobriety.

To demonstrate communities' commitment, the in-kind donations support individuals in their recovery journey, challenging the negative stereotypes associated with addiction.

Through tangible support, the barangay and local government unit help break down barriers and promote a more inclusive and compassionate society where drug surrenderers feel a sense of worthiness and gain confidence in overcoming addiction.

The in-kind donations can be given as rewards or incentives for drug surrenderers who demonstrate progress in their recovery. This reinforcement of positive behavior encourages individuals to stay committed to their sobriety and motivates them to continue making positive changes in their lives. It reinforces the idea that recovery is a rewarding and worthwhile journey, increasing the chances of long-term success.

Livelihood Program

The livelihood program seeks to improve the economic status of the participants during treatment. One benefited from the cash-for-work program launched by the barangay and local government unit of Baungon that was prioritized as a reward/benefit for their recovery. Participant # 3 said,

“Ang barangay ug ang munisipyo sa Baungon usa ra silag program kay gihatag man sa Municipyo ang CBRP sa barangay. Pang kuhaon mi sa barangay nga trabahante para sa cash for work para atleast silbi benepisyong namo sa pag recover. Magbuhat me ug waiting shed ug kanal (The barangay and the municipality of Baungon have only one program, the CBRP. The barangay handled the CBRP. They will hire us to work in the barangay if there is cash for work. This is our drug recovery benefit. We will build waiting shed and drainage).”

Livelihood programs, such as micro-finance and small business development, provided by the barangay and local government unit can help drug surrenderers create a source of income and reduce their financial stress (Natividad and colleagues, 2018). In comparison, the DOLE created the Kabuhayan Program to give drug surrender jobs (Department of Labor and Employment 2020). Lastly, a law also demanded the provision of livelihood and training programs to drug surrenderers (Dangerous Drug Board, 2016).

Livelihood programs provide drug surrenderers opportunities to develop skills, gain employment, or start businesses. Livelihood programs facilitate the reintegration of drug surrenderers into the workforce and broader society. By acquiring vocational skills, training, or job placement assistance, individuals can overcome the employment gaps or barriers they may have faced due to addiction. These social connections enhance their social capital by providing access to information, resources, and support, which can contribute to their successful recovery and long-term well-being.

Providing opportunities for individuals to engage in productive work, contribute to society, and support themselves and their families, these programs can help restore a positive self-image for drug surrenderers. It is crucial to reduce recidivism rates among drug surrenderers by equipping them with the skills, knowledge, and opportunities for sustainable employment or entrepreneurship; they are less likely to engage in criminal activities or return to substance abuse.

The Livelihood programs promote the development of positive social bonds and relationships; they can also benefit not only the individual drug surrenderers but also their families and communities.

In helping drug surrenderers become self-supporting and economically stable, the programs contribute to overall community development. That may reduce the economic burden on families, strengthen family ties, and improve the quality of life for all community members. These programs can help drug surrenderers develop new skills, create a source of income, and reduce their risk of relapse.

Voluntary Works

Voluntary work is one thing that can help people who have been addicted to drugs get better. Volunteering makes you feel good about yourself and gives you a sense of accomplishment because you are helping other people and the community. Volunteering can also give people a sense of pride and identity. One participant recalled an experience of joining voluntary works at a barangay, participant # 3 shared,

”Naay programa ang barangay nga baranggayan na mag kinahanglan silag volunteer. Ubanon ko para magdala sa gamit sa mga BHW labina kung mag timbang sila sa mga bata. Kung naa sad bisita ang barangay magluto ko, ug mag serve ug pagkaon sa mga bisita. Sa pag join nako sa baranggayan gahalikay nako sa mga kahilayan sa gawas kay busy naman ko sa activity sa barangay (The barangay has a program where it needs volunteers. I will accompany them to carry the BHW equipment, especially when they weigh the children. When the barangay has guests, I cook and serve food. When I joined the barangayan program, I avoided outside pleasures because I was busy with barangay activities).”

Manalo and colleagues (2019) found out that drug surrenderers who participated in community service activities reported higher levels of self-esteem and better mental health outcomes than those who did not participate in community service activities.

Natividad and colleagues (2018) added that volunteering in community events or participating in environmental projects can help drug surrenderers develop a sense of responsibility and accountability. Aside from that, it allows them to be recognized by other people, making them less likely to get back from drug addiction (Afzal & Hussain, 2020).

Voluntary works provided by the barangay and local government unit can positively impact the successful recovery of drug surrenderers after completing a community-based rehabilitation program. These voluntary works can help drug surrenderers develop a sense of purpose, build social connections, and improve their self-esteem.

Voluntary work provides by engaging in activities that contribute to the community's welfare; individuals develop a sense of accomplishment, self-worth, and belonging. These social interactions provide support, encouragement, and a network of individuals who share common goals, values, and experiences, which can contribute to their successful recovery; engaging in community-based projects, individuals can acquire job-related skills, improve their communication and teamwork abilities, and learn problem-solving and leadership skills.

This positive identity formation strengthens their commitment to recovery and helps them challenge the negative stereotypes associated with addiction. By engaging in voluntary activities alongside individuals in recovery, community members better understand addiction as a complex issue and overcome stigmatizing attitudes. When drug surrenderers involve in community projects, the barangay and local government unit foster a collective spirit and encourage them to work together towards shared goals. Active participation in voluntary work can help the drug surrenderers to become role models, inspiring others and promoting positive change within their community.

Membership in Organization Support

Membership in Organization was another theme that emerged in the study. Membership in the Organization provides the participant with instrumental support to join in societal events. Only one had a civic organization among the participants who underwent in-depth interviews and focus group discussions.

Francis explained that he participated in the community services conducted by his fraternity. These activities were: feeding programs, tree planting, and gift-giving to selected kindergartens in the remote areas of Baungon. Participant # 3 maintained,

”Ang support nga gihatag sa akua sa fraternity kay kada hinapos sa bulan mag apil ko sa feeding program. Apil ko permemente kay naay multa kung dili mag apil. Naa dayun attendance, mag ambag-ambag dayun mi ug singkwenta pesos para amoa ifeeding program sa mga malnourished nga bata sa kindergarten. Mag tree planting pod mi sa mga barangay barangay kung naay gusto magpatanom sa kahoy. Maghatag pod kami sa mga tsinelas didto sa mga lagyo nga lugar. Mag ambag-ambag dayun mi para sa notebook, ballpen, ug papel isulod sa expanded envelope para ihatag sa mga bata kada ikatulo sa bulan (The support given to me by the fraternity is that at the end of the month, I participate in the feeding program. I permanently joined because there is a fine if I don't participate. There is attendance. We will contribute fifty pesos for our feeding program for malnourished children in kindergarten. We will plant in barangays if anyone wants us to plant a tree. We also give slippers to remote areas. We will then contribute notebooks, ball pens, and papers and put them in expanded envelopes for the children every third of the month).”

Membership in an organization can help drug surrenderers develop a sense of belonging and build social connections (Manalo and colleagues, 2019). As mentioned by Natividad and colleagues (2018), drug surrenderers who were members of a support group reported better social functioning and reduced risk of relapse compared to those who were not.

Statement of the Problem # 4. Is there a significant difference between drug surrenderers' perceived social support in terms of age, gender, civil status, educational attainment, and membership in organization?

Tables 5-7 presented the results of significant differences between drug surrenderers' perceived social support in terms of age, civil status, and educational attainment, and it was tested using the Kruskal-Wallis method. While tables 8-9 were interpreted using the Mann-Whitney method to test the significant difference in the perceived emotional support of the respondents according to their gender and membership in the Organization.

Table 5. Significant Difference on the Micro-Level (Emotional Support) of the Subject Participants Classified According to their Age

Age	Mean Rank	N	Chi-Square Statistic	p-value	Remark
20-29 years old	68.53	38	5.23	.041	Significant
30-39 years old	73.13	64			
40-49 years old	67.61	33			
50-59 years old	53.63	4			

The result of emotional support on the drug surrenderers according to their age is summarized in Table 2.3 using the Kruskal-Wallis method; the emotional support given to the drug surrenderers' was significantly different across their age brackets. It revealed that those 30-39 years were getting the most support, while those 50-59 got the least support after participating in a community-based rehabilitation program.

The findings suggest that age is an essential factor to consider when providing emotional support to drug surrenderers and that interventions should be tailored to meet the specific needs of different age groups (Nguyen et al., 2016). As Hutchison, Cox, and Frings (2018) explain, younger individuals may have more social connections and support networks than older individuals.

This only means that the emotional support given to drug surrenderers differed significantly across their age brackets because age can influence the availability and composition of an individual's social support network. Younger drug surrenderers have friends, significant others, and family members who can offer understanding and relatable support. At the same time, older drug surrenderers established relationships that can guide and assist them during their recovery journey. Therefore, the social dynamics and support systems available at different ages can shape the emotional support received.

Further, younger individuals may be more likely to have friends and family members who are also in their age group and can provide emotional support during rehabilitation. Additionally, younger individuals may be more likely to be employed and have access to resources. On the other hand, older individuals may be more isolated and have fewer social connections, making it more difficult for them to receive emotional support. They may also have more health problems and financial difficulties, which can further limit their ability to access resources and support.

Table 6. Significant Difference on the Micro-Level (Emotional Support) of the Subject Participants Classified According to their Civil Status

Civil Status	Mean Rank	N	Chi-Square Statistic	p-value	Remark
Married	70.14	98	.005	.998	Not Significant
Live-in partner	69.75	24			
With romantic relationship	69.53	17			

The table showed the result of the significant difference in the micro-level emotional support of respondents classified according to their civil status is summarized in Table 2.4. The emotional support given to the drug surrenderers was not significantly different across their civil status based on the Kruskal-Wallis method used. This only means that being married, having a live-in partner, and having a close relationship with a particular individual have nothing to do with the emotional support given to the drug surrenderers.

The United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (2017) discussed that a drug surrenderer who does not have significant other is likelier to have a low level of support and a higher chance of completing the program and maintaining sobriety (Kelly, Yeterian, and Deane, 2018). According to Mericle et al. (2009), marriage positively influenced drug treatment outcomes. Moreover, in a study by O'Malley et al. (2012), peer support programs like Alcoholics Anonymous showed significant positive effects on recovery outcomes for unmarried individuals.

The possible reasons why the emotional support given to drug surrenderers may not vary significantly across their civil status due to several factors: For instance, shared experiences of addiction, regardless of civil status, drug surrenderers often share similar experiences of addiction, including the emotional struggles, challenges, and consequences associated with substance abuse. These shared experiences create a common ground for emotional support, as individuals can relate to one another's feelings and provide

empathetic understanding, irrespective of their civil status.

Structural factors have influenced the drug surrenderers' emotional support, such as access to treatment programs, availability of support groups, or resources for recovery. These factors may be influenced by policy, healthcare systems, and community organizations rather than civil status.

While civil status may not be a primary determinant of emotional support, it is essential to note that individuals of different civil statuses may face unique challenges and circumstances related to addiction and recovery. Therefore, married and unmarried drug surrenderers need social support after completing a community-based rehabilitation program because it significantly improves their chances of maintaining sobriety and improving their overall quality of life. Social support can come in various forms, including from family members, friends, support groups, and healthcare professionals.

Table 7. Significant Difference on the Micro-Level (Emotional Support) of the Subject Participants Classified According to their Educational Attainment

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Chi-Square Statistic</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remark</i>
Elementary level	62.65	48	5.757	.021	Significant
Some high school level	59.13	15			
High School graduate	74.17	49			
Vocational	85.50	14			
Bachelor's degree	77.27	13			

The results on the emotional support received by respondents regarding their educational attainment interpreted by the Kruskal-Wallis method show a significant difference. This only means that drug surrenderers with vocational courses are more likely to receive tremendous support from their friends, significant other, and family rather than those with bachelor's degrees, high school graduate/high school level, and elementary level.

Vocational training and stable employment seem to contribute to lower relapse rates of individuals with drug dependency (Coates, Chin, and Chung, 2011). Perhaps, completing vocational training might lead to more work activity resulting in positive life-changing situations, which could be related to a reduced substance (Geyer, 2009). Lastly, employment is significant in successfully treating drug abusers and offering vocational services among individuals seeking addiction treatment is highly important (Doostian et al., 2019).

The educational attainment shows a significant difference regarding the emotional support received by the drug surrenderers. This only denotes that educational attainment often correlates with access to resources, including information about addiction, treatment options, and support services. Higher levels of education can provide individuals with more excellent knowledge and awareness of available resources, leading to more informed decisions about seeking emotional support. Those with higher educational attainment may be better equipped to navigate the healthcare system, find appropriate support networks, and engage in self-help resources.

Social support can come in many forms and from many sources, including friends, family members, significant others, and community organizations. A drug surrenderer with vocational courses or training had a higher level of emotional support received because they are equipped with knowledge, experiences, skills, and competencies required in any particular occupation for the additional labor market. However, individuals with higher education levels may have access to different types of support systems than those with vocational training.

Therefore, educational attainment can influence emotional support; it is not the sole determinant. Emotional support is a complex social process influenced by various intersecting factors such as socioeconomic status, race, gender, and individual circumstances.

Table 8. Significant Difference on the Micro-Level (Emotional Support) of the Subject Participants Classified According to their Gender

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mann-Whitney U Test</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remark</i>
Male	70.91	136	80.50	.027	Significant
Female	28.83	3			

Based on the results from the Mann-Whitney method on, the emotional support of respondents about their gender is statistically significant. The male drug surrenderers have a higher mean than the female drug users, which means that most males have received the emotional support they needed from their friends, significant other, and family.

As explained by Marsh & Markham (2014), women are more likely to rely on romantic partners and family members, while men have more extensive social networks outside the family structure. Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration (2019) mentions that women also face more negative social consequences for being ostracized in their community or losing custody of their children. It was supported by Gordon et al. (2021) that gender appears to be most strongly associated with substance use in this

population. Males are generally found to be more risk-takers, perhaps influenced by the freedoms and privileges they have, than women. Gender roles and expectations were one of the reasons why the emotional support of drug surrenderers was statistically different based on their gender. Societal norms and expectations can influence the type and amount of emotional support available to drug surrenderers. Traditional gender roles often dictate that men should be self-reliant and stoic, while women are expected to be nurturing and emotionally expressive. These gender expectations can shape the emotional support individuals receive, with men potentially facing barriers seeking emotional support due to stigma and societal pressure to appear strong.

Aside from that stigma and social perception, women may face particular challenges related to societal views of maternal roles, femininity, and the perception of deviating from expected behaviors, and both genders have different support networks such as friends, family, or community groups, which provide different types and levels of emotional support.

This only means that drug use and addiction affect both men and women, and both genders face different challenges in seeking and receiving help. However, women are often more stigmatized and marginalized in drug use and addiction treatment, which can affect their support levels.

Table 9. Significant Difference on the Micro (Instrumental Support) of the Subject Participants Classified According to their Membership to an Organization

Membership	Mean Rank	N	Mann-Whitney U Test	p-value	Remark
No	68.82	124	784.00	.320	Not Significant
Yes	79.73	15			

No significant difference was found in the instrumental support of respondents based on the result from the Mann-Whitney method regarding their membership to an organization, which means that membership in an organization has nothing to do with the instrumental support they received. The reason behind this is that most of the drug surrenderers claimed that they were no longer active in their respective organizations, and some did not have an organization prior to the study.

According to a study by Hanlon, Flynn, and Desai (2016), membership in a specific organization is not significantly related to the instrumental support drug surrenderers receive after completing a community-based rehabilitation program. Furthermore, a systematic review by Evans and Hser (2016) found that social support was positively correlated with improved outcomes among individuals with substance abuse disorders. However, the study found no significant associations between social network characteristics, such as organization membership, and treatment outcomes.

The data revealed that no significant difference was found in the instrumental support of respondents according to their membership in an organization. This means that drug surrenderers who join an organization go through a socialization process that helps them internalize the Organization's values and norms. If the Organization has effective socialization processes that promote consistent emotional support for drug surrenderers, it can lead to similar support being provided regardless of membership.

Drug surrenderers may form their social support networks within the Organization, irrespective of membership status. These networks can provide emotional support to each other based on shared experiences and challenges related to substance abuse, and if the Organization actively works to reduce the stigma associated with substance abuse and supports an inclusive environment, members may be more likely to offer emotional support to drug surrenderers regardless of their membership status.

Thus, most respondents viewed membership in an organization as unnecessary in their recovery because they are more attached to personnel from the community-based rehabilitation program, especially to their co- drug surrenderers. The community-based rehabilitation program creates bonds and solidarity amongst them that fast-track recovery. Because of this, they motivate and help each other to continuously refrain from using drugs and live their life with meaning.

Statement of the Problem # 5: How does Social Support Affect Drug Surrenderers' Recovery Process?

Effect of Emotional Support to Family Drug Surrenderers

This part of the study presents the effect of emotional support on drug surrenderers. Based on the in-depth interview and focus group discussion, one participant shared how emotional support helped him assume family responsibility. The emotional support he received made him accountable for his family's daily needs right after post-treatment. Participant # 3 remarked,

“Sauna kay mag maoy ko sa balay labina kulangan ko sa pagkaon nga naa sa lamesa akong ipanglabay ang plato. Pero karun ang kabag-ohan kay ako na mag luto, manlimpiyo, mag sag-ob ug tubig ug mangitag trabaho aron makatabang sa pamilya para ipalit sa bugas (Before, I throw away the plate when I'm home, especially when there is insufficient food on the table. But now the change is that I cook, clean, fetch water, and look for a job to help the family buy rice).”

Research conducted by Sherman, Bigelow, and Obst (2019) found that family involvement was associated with a higher likelihood of completing treatment and achieving abstinence. Similarly, a study by Granfield and Cloud (1999) found that emotional support and

encouragement from family members helped individuals overcome feelings of isolation and stigma associated with addiction and ultimately helped them to maintain sobriety.

Emotional support from family members plays a crucial role in facilitating the social integration of drug surrenderers. Family members can be role models, demonstrating healthy coping strategies, effective communication skills, and positive problem-solving techniques.

Expressing one's belief in their loved ones can provide consistent encouragement and positively influence their self-confidence and determination. Addiction often results in strained family relationships, trust issues, and emotional turmoil. By offering understanding, empathy, and non-judgmental support, family members can create a safe space for individuals in recovery to express and process their emotions.

A robust support system can provide by a family if a drug surrenderer stays accountable, navigate challenges, and resist the temptations associated with addiction. This only means that family support provides a foundation of acceptance and understanding that helps individuals rebuild trust, repair relationships, and reintegrate into the family unit and broader society.

Therefore, emotional support from family members to drug surrenderers recognizes the importance of social relationships, social learning, and social integration in recovery. By offering understanding, encouragement, and a supportive environment, family members contribute to individuals' emotional well-being, motivation, and resilience in recovery. The relevance of emotional support lies in its ability to foster positive social bonds, address relational dynamics, and create a foundation for successful recovery and reintegration into society.

Effect of Emotional Support on Significant Other Drug Surrenderers

The effect of emotional support on a drug surrenderer's significant other was another important theme of this study. The following sub-themes were developed from the responses to in-depth interviews and focus group discussions: (a) Monetary Support; and (b) Time Management.

Monetary Support

Monetary support was one of the sub-themes that appeared in the themes about the effect of emotional support on drug surrenderers' significant others. Participant # 2 shared his experience about sharing monetary obligations with his wife and their household. Unlike when he was using drugs, he did not give money to his wife because he was spending it on drugs. He shared,

“Before gagamit ko sa drugs, akong asawa walay pakialam sa akong kwarta ug unsa akong paliton kay kung ting sweldo na nako dili naman maabot ka misis kay gibayad na nako sa akong utang ug gipalit na daan sa drugs. Sa pagka karun mag share nami ug bayrunon sa kurente ug hatagan na nako siya ug kwarta. Karun sad makapalit nasad ko ug gamit sa balay ug naka parenovate na (Before when I was into drugs, my wife didn't care about my money or what I would buy. When I got my salary, it wouldn't reach my wife because I already paid off my debt and bought drugs. As of now, we share the payment of the electricity bill, and I give her money. Now I can buy things for the house, and I have already renovated it).”

Individuals who received financial assistance after rehabilitation had a higher chance of staying clean and maintaining sobriety (Lansangan & Lirio, 2016). Similarly, a study by Paguirigan et al. (2018) found that providing job opportunities to drug surrenderers significantly reduced their likelihood of relapsing. The World Health Organization (2019) emphasizes that a lack of financial stability can be a significant stressor and trigger for relapse. In comparison, financial difficulties and dissatisfaction with one's financial status can lead to marital conflict and divorce (Copur, 2016).

Monetary support provides drug surrenderers the means to achieve economic stability, which is crucial for their recovery. It can cover the costs associated with these services, ensuring that individuals have access to the resources they need to aid their recovery process effectively. Financial support empowers individuals to become self-sufficient, contributing members of society and reduces the risk of relapse due to financial insecurity.

These factors contribute to an improved sense of self-worth, satisfaction, and fulfillment, which is essential to successful recovery. On the contrary, financial instability can drive individuals to resort to criminal activities, such as theft or drug dealing, to fund their substance abuse. That is why monetary support promotes social equity and support for drug surrenderers because addiction disproportionately affects individuals from marginalized or disadvantaged backgrounds. Individuals can focus on their recovery and rebuild their lives by removing financial barriers.

Thus, monetary support recognizes the influence of economic factors, social equity, and resource access in recovery. By providing financial assistance, society addresses the economic dimensions of addiction and helps create a supportive environment that facilitates successful recovery and reintegration into society.

Time Management

One of the sub-themes in the study was time management, which helped the people who took part make good use of their time. During the in-depth interview and focus group discussion, one participant shared how time management keeps his relationship with his wife intact and makes him sensitive to her feelings.

“Ang kabag-ohan kay dili na nako gaawayon akong asawa dili na nako siya yawa-yawaon. Dili nasad siya muhilak nga walay rason. Pero sa kanang panahon nga wala pako nag graduate sa CBRP program. Dugay kaayo ko maka uli sa among balay kay mag laag laag pa bisn asa. Naay impact ang programa sa ako kay kabalo nako mag manage sa akoang oras. Mag uli na dayun ko ditso if paulion nako sa ako misis (The change is that I no longer fight with my wife. I no longer demonize her. She does not cry in vain anymore. But at that time, I did not graduate from the CBRP program. It took me a long time to return to our house because I wandered everywhere. The program impacts me because I know how to manage my time and if my wife wants me to go home. I will go home immediately)” participant # 2 shared.

One study by Choi and Kim (2019) found that effective time management was positively associated with relational communication and problem-solving skills. Additionally, Lee and Eun (2018) highlighted the importance of having a specific daily schedule to help individuals in recovery maintain sobriety and create a sense of structure. Furthermore, a study by Leung et al. (2019) emphasized the importance of maintaining healthy relationships and engaging in positive activities, such as exercise and hobbies, which were crucial steps in maintaining long-term sobriety. Effective time management helps individuals allocate time for essential activities such as therapy sessions, support group meetings, exercise, self-care, and pursuing personal goals. Individuals can track their progress and measure their achievements by allocating time for goal-oriented activities. In the past, substance abuse may have consumed a significant portion of their daily activities. This sense of responsibility fosters self-discipline, integrity, and a commitment to their recovery process. Support group meetings, therapy sessions, counseling appointments, and other recovery-related activities require time and commitment.

Time management is crucial in maintaining a healthy relationship with a significant other who is a drug surrenderer after completing a community-based rehabilitation program. Effective time management can help both partners overcome challenges and create a sense of stability and routine.

Therefore, time management recognizes the role of social structure, personal agency, and the Organization of daily activities in the recovery process. Effective time management helps drug surrenderers establish a structured routine, set goals, and make productive use of their time. It promotes accountability, responsibility, and self-management skills, vital for successful recovery and reintegration into society. By managing their time effectively, individuals can create a supportive and balanced lifestyle that supports their sobriety and overall well-being.

Significant others, such as spouses, partners, or close friends, are vital in providing a supportive and caring environment. They offer understanding, empathy, and encouragement, which can positively influence the recovery journey. By providing encouragement, setting boundaries, and engaging in activities that do not involve drugs or alcohol, significant others help shape the social environment around the individual in recovery. Addiction often leads to strained relationships, mistrust, and emotional turmoil within significant relationships. Emotional support helps address these issues by providing a safe space for individuals to express their feelings, process emotions, and heal relationship wounds.

When individuals feel supported, loved, and cared for, they are more likely to stay committed to their recovery journey. The support and understanding provided by significant others help counteract these negative experiences by providing a sense of belonging and acceptance. This process helps create a supportive and positive relationship dynamic that supports the individual's recovery journey. Emotional support from significant others allows for social learning and the development of practical coping skills.

This only means that emotional support from significant others acknowledges the significance of social relationships, social norms, and social support networks in the recovery process. By providing understanding, empathy, and encouragement, significant others contribute to individuals' emotional well-being, motivation, and resilience in recovery. The relevance of emotional support lies in its ability to foster positive relationship dynamics, strengthen social networks, and create an environment conducive to successful recovery.

Effects of Community-Based Rehabilitation Program on Drug Surrenderers

The community-based rehabilitation program has significantly improved the lives of drug surrenderers with the programs and services it has conducted and provided. The theme is comprised of four unique sub-themes: (a) Acts of Gratefulness; (b) Behavioral Transformation; (c) Physical Transformation; and (d) Spiritual Transformation.

Acts of Gratefulness

One participant showed an act of gratefulness toward the community-based rehabilitation program done to her that changed her life condition. Participant # 8 expressed her thoughts,

“Nagpasalamat ko sa programa kay gitagaan ko ug chance nga mag bag-o kay kung wala ang CBRP basin matigulang nagud ko nga adik adik (I am thankful for the program because it allowed me to change. After all, without the CBRP, I might have grown old and become an addict).”

Motivational interviewing is a method to work with ambivalence and help patients explore their reasons for changing from drug use. The essential elements of motivational interviewing include: expressing empathy, developing discrepancy awareness (helping the clients see the discrepancy between their drug use and their goals, and avoiding argumentation – rolling with resistance. (United Nations

Office on Drugs and Crime 2016).

Expressing gratitude acknowledges the support, care, and encouragement provided by community members, volunteers, and professionals involved in the rehabilitation program is essential. When individuals receive gratitude and appreciation for their commitment to change and their steps toward sobriety, it boosts their self-esteem, motivation, and confidence. This sense of purpose gives individuals a greater sense of identity, personal fulfillment, and motivation to maintain their recovery and continue making a positive impact.

Acts of gratefulness from the community-based rehabilitation program provide social support and encouragement to drug surrenderers. Expressing gratitude demonstrates that individuals in recovery are valued members of the community-based rehabilitation program, capable of change and growth. As individuals express their gratitude, they feel responsible for giving back and contributing positively to the community-based rehabilitation program. Acts of gratefulness empower drug surrenderers by recognizing their agency and the positive changes they have made. Expressing gratitude reinforces the notion that individuals have the power to overcome addiction and create a better future for themselves.

So, acts of gratefulness within the Community-Based Rehabilitation Program acknowledge the importance of social support, positive reinforcement, and reciprocal relationships in the recovery process. By fostering a sense of connectedness, social reintegration, and empowerment, acts of gratefulness contribute to drug surrenderers' successful recovery journey. They create a supportive and inclusive community environment that recognizes the value of individuals in recovery and encourages their continued progress toward a substance-free life.

Behavioral Transformation

Participants observed behavioral transformations after attending the community-based rehabilitation program. Two participants expressed behavioral change about the shift of attitude, and one participant about the sense of responsibility they perceived in themselves.

“So nagpasalamat ko sa CBRP kay positive ang result ug gitagaan ko ug chance ug time nga mag bag-o para pod mawala tong dating ginabuhay nga daotan (So I am thankful to the CBRP because the result was positive, and they gave me a chance and time to change to get rid of the bad things I used to do),” said participant # 9, who is a 38 year-old drug surrenderer. Participant # 5, whose 24 year-old also shared similar sentiments, “Sa akong dako man gud siyag impact kay nabag-o man gud nako akoang kaugalingon” (It had a significant impact on me because I changed myself).”

Further, participant # 7, a 46-year-old drug surrenderer, observed a sense of responsibility for himself and his family during his recovery.

“Dako kaayog kaayuhan ang gihatag sa programa sa akong kay sauna naa ra kadalanan mag laag-laag Karun naa nako sa balay kauban akong pamilya (The program has given me many benefits because I used to wander around the streets. Now I'm at home with my family).”

According to various studies and research, acts of gratefulness and expressions of gratitude can positively impact and aid in the recovery process of drug surrenderers. Further, gratitude can increase activity in the prefrontal cortex, and heightened emotional processing can lead to improved emotional regulation and decision-making (Zahn et al., 2013). Emmons and McCullough, in 2003, found that practicing gratitude can help them stay motivated in their recovery journey and strengthen their support system.

Behavioral transformation helps drug surrenderers to adopt healthier behaviors and lifestyles. When drug surrenderers witness positive changes in their peers in the rehabilitation program, it reinforces the belief that recovery is possible. It motivates them to engage in similar behavioral transformations because it reduces the stigma associated with addiction and supports the social reintegration of drug surrenderers.

As drug surrenderers adopt healthier behaviors, they are more likely to form positive relationships with community members with similar values and goals. These supportive networks provide drug surrenderers with emotional support, accountability, and resources to facilitate their recovery. As more drug surrenderers within the community engage in positive behavioral changes, it can influence community institutions, policies, and practices related to addiction and recovery. This systemic change supports the sustainability of the rehabilitation program and creates an environment that promotes successful recovery for drug surrenderers.

In the end, acts of behavioral transformation within the Community-Based Rehabilitation Program recognize the importance of social norms, social support, role modeling, and community engagement in the recovery process. By promoting positive behavioral changes, the program creates a supportive and empowering social environment that fosters successful recovery, reduces stigma, and supports the social reintegration of drug surrenderers. It also contributes to systemic and environmental changes that sustain a community's recovery culture.

Physical Transformation

The physical transformation was one of the benefits felt by a participant in the program. Participant # 4, a 55-year-old drug surrenderer,

has spoken about his appreciation of his body alteration.

“Dako kaayo ug natabang sa akong ang CBRP kay wala nako nag gamit sa droga pag usab. Sauna akoang kubo walay tuyo, suka ug asin. Bisan ultimo 500 nga kwarta nabilin, ako gamitin para ipalit sa droga sa CDO. Pero karun nitambok nako kay mukaon naman ug sakto, maayo na ang tulog. Akong timbang before kay 55 kilos karun 67 kilos na kay nanambok naman (The CBRP was very helpful for me because I didn't use drugs again. My hut has no tuyo, vinegar, or salt. Even with the last 500 money left, I will use it to buy drugs in CDO. But now I'm gaining weight because I'm eating right and sleeping enough. My weight before was 55 kilos; now it's 67 kilos because I gained weight).”

According to Amato et al. (2015), physical exercise can positively impact the recovery process for drug users by reducing symptoms of anxiety and depression and improving overall well-being. Additionally, Brown et al. (2016) found that a healthy diet can play a crucial role in recovery, specifically in reducing cravings. A review by Pizzorno and Murray (2013) noted that holistic approaches to addiction recovery, which can include physical aspects such as exercise and nutrition, have been shown to have better long-term success rates than traditional treatments. Physical transformation can be a significant aspect of the recovery process for drug surrenderers. Many may come into treatment with physical ailments such as malnutrition, liver damage, and infections. As they undergo detoxification and rehabilitation, they must address these physical issues and change their lifestyle to improve their overall health.

Physical transformation is a symbolic change that signifies a break from the past and a commitment to a new way of life. By engaging in physical well-being activities, such as exercise, proper nutrition, and self-care, drug surrenderers signal their dedication to recovery and a healthier lifestyle. When individuals visibly demonstrate positive physical changes, such as improved health, vitality, and grooming, it can positively influence how others perceive them. Engaging in regular exercise, adopting a balanced diet, and practicing self-care promote physical wellness, increase energy levels, and improve overall health.

Improving physical health contributes to individuals' personal well-being and provides them with the physical strength and resilience needed to navigate the challenges of recovery successfully. This sense of discipline and routine extends beyond physical activities and can positively influence other aspects of drug surrenderers' lives, such as adhering to therapy sessions, support group meetings, and other recovery-related commitments. This ripple effect of inspiration and role modeling contributes to a supportive community environment that fosters successful recovery and encourages drug surrenderers to embrace physical transformation as part of their journey.

Spiritual Transformation

During the interview, one participant revealed his spiritual transformation after therapy. The participant described his active participation in church mass.

“Sa times nga nag gamit ko sa drugs, dili ko mag simba maskin silingan ra namo ang simbahan. Pero sa paghuman nakog apil sa CBRP permente nako mag samba (When I was using drugs, I didn't go to church, even though the church was our neighbor. But after I joined the CBRP, I always go to church).”

Spiritual transformation is the key to maintaining long-term sobriety (Kelly et al., 2013). Miller et al. (2008) found that spiritual transformation was associated with decreased substance use and improved life satisfaction in individuals recovering from drug addiction. Principles of spirituality, like mindfulness practices, meditation, and yoga, can help individuals connect with their inner selves and transform their worldviews (Zeng et al., 2020). Based on the board regulation no. 4 Series of 2016 of the Dangerous Drug Board (2016), the purpose of spiritual/faith-based interventions for drug responders was to use moral and spiritual principles, doctrines, and writings to influence the well-being of a substance user.

Spiritual transformation gives drug surrenderers a sense of meaning and purpose in their recovery process. Engaging in spiritual practices, such as meditation, prayer, or connecting with higher values or beliefs, helps individuals reflect on their lives, values, and the impact of their actions. Developing a spiritual connection or belief system gives drug surrenderers a framework to draw upon during challenging times. Engaging in spiritual practices often involves reflecting on personal values, ethical principles, and the impact of one's actions on oneself and others.

It encourages drug surrenderers to self-reflection and personal Engaging in spiritual practices often involves introspection, examining one's past behaviors and choices, and seeking forgiveness or reconciliation. The social support and connection within a spiritual community can strengthen individuals' commitment to their recovery and provide a network of understanding peers.

Thus, spiritual transformation within the Community-Based Rehabilitation Program recognizes the importance of meaning, values, community, and personal growth in recovery. By incorporating spiritual practices and fostering a supportive spiritual environment, the program promotes successful recovery, enhances well-being, and provides individuals with the tools and support to lead a fulfilling life free from addiction. Spiritual transformation contributes to individuals' holistic well-being and ability to reintegrate positively into the broader social fabric.

Quantitative and qualitative research methods serve different purposes and provide complementary insights into a study. While quantitative research focuses on numerical data and statistical analysis, qualitative research explores subjective experiences,

perceptions, and meanings through non-numerical data such as interviews, observations, and open-ended questions.

In the study, quantitative and qualitative results are valuable because quantitative data provides objective measures and allows for statistical analysis, revealing patterns, trends, and relationships between variables. For example, quantitative data can provide information on the number of individuals receiving social support, the frequency of support received, the types of support provided, or the impact of social support on drug rehabilitation outcomes. These numerical findings help researchers understand the prevalence and magnitude of social support and its quantitative impact (Creswell & Plano, 2017).

While the qualitative data of the study helps to uncover the subjective experiences, perceptions, and meanings related to social support, through qualitative methods such as interviews or open-ended survey responses, researchers can explore the in-depth narratives and personal perspectives of drug surrenderers on the instrumental support received from barangay, local government unit, membership to an organization, and the effects of social on their recovery process. Qualitative findings can shed light on social support's quality, nature, and nuances, capturing detailed descriptions of how social support affects individuals' emotions, motivations, and behaviors (Braun & Clarke, 2019).

By combining quantitative and qualitative approaches, researchers can comprehensively understand social support among drug surrenderers in the community-based rehabilitation program. This mixed-methods exploratory sequential approach allows for a more holistic analysis and interpretation of the complex social dynamics and individual experiences, leading to a deeper understanding of the phenomenon under study.

Conclusions

The drug surrenderers have a very high level of social support from friends, significant others, and family; therefore, social support is a significant factor in the successful reintegration of drug surrenderers after the community-based rehabilitation program.

The barangay, local government unit, and membership organization provided social services for drug surrenderers like after-care sessions, community service, financial support, in-kind donations, voluntary works, livelihood programs, and membership in the organizations. Therefore, the barangay, local government unit, and community organizations followed and implemented the national government's program for drug surrenderers.

There is a significant difference in the social support of drug surrenderers based on their age brackets; therefore, there is a need to develop programs and support for every age bracket.

There is no significant difference in the social support of drug surrenderers based on their civil status; therefore, being married, having a live-in partner, or having a romantic relationship with a particular individual has nothing to do with the emotional support given to them because the drug surrenderers have equally received an effective and supportive social support system from their significant other.

There is a significant difference in the social support of drug surrenderers based on their educational attainment; therefore, those drug surrenderers who had vocational courses are more likely to receive a greater amount of support from their friends, significant other, and family than those drug surrenderers who had a bachelor's degree, are high school graduates or have some high school diplomas, and have no schooling completed.

There is a significant difference in the social support of drug surrenderers based on gender; therefore, most males receive the emotional support they need from their friends, significant others, and family more than females.

There was no significant difference found in the instrumental support of subject respondents based on their membership to an organization; therefore, membership in an organization has nothing to do with the instrumental support they received.

The support from friends, a significant other, and family greatly impacted their recovery process. Therefore, the drug surrenderers' friends, significant other, and family play an essential role in a successful recovery from drug addiction.

The community-based rehabilitation program in Baungon may continue to provide services to drug surrenderers. Its holistic approach to treating drug responders may be further strengthened and developed. Based on Sustainable Development Goal # 4 of Quality Education, this study can contribute to understanding the social support needs of drug surrenderers in community-based rehabilitation programs. This knowledge can help inform educational interventions and programs to support these individuals.

The DILG/LGU, MHO, MSWDO, DEPED, PNP, LFC, SB, PESO, Business Sector/Stakeholders, Community Support Group, and Service Provider should carry out their respective functions and responsibilities to offer excellent services to participants, including the peace, justice, and strong institutions, by examining the social support provided to drug surrenderers, contribute to understanding the role of community-based rehabilitation programs in promoting justice, peace, and influential institutions in addressing drug-related issues as the Sustainable Development Goal # 16, and including:

The Department of Interior and Local Government/Local Government Unit in the municipality, as a national government agency, continue to promote peace and order, ensure public safety, and strengthen local government capacity to deliver services to the general populace effectively, as well as the CBRP secretariat charged with maintaining records, collecting data, and recording the attendance

of the community-based rehabilitation program participants.

The medical field sector, represented by the Municipal Health Office, must persist in conducting drug testing of the program's participants as baseline information, provide first aid in emergencies, assist in the charting of each participant's progress, serve as a resource in the CBRP module, and provide technical assistance when required.

The Municipal Social Worker and Development Office and Department of Education need to consistently keep sharing the responsibility for making decisions regarding issues and concerns arising from the conduct of the program, coordinate and link with other members in the daily operation of the program, engage in case management, assess, counsel, and their families, and offer guidance and advice on life decisions and opportunities to drug participants.

The Philippine National Police strengthens its activities on tokhang to produce a list of drug personalities that will serve as the baseline for those invited to be assessed and participate in the CBRP. Ensure the safety of those who attend seminars, symposia, training, and conferences on the effective handling and counseling of drug responders and surrenderers; update the list of the total number of drug surrenderers; and conduct the evaluation and processing of the names of those who graduated from the CBRP program.

The local finance committee shall actively assist the chief executive regarding financial decisions.

As legislative body members, the Sanggunian Bayan Committee Chairs on Social Services, Education, and Laws and Rules enhance their social services, education, and law expertise by crafting legal measures to assist the municipality's development initiatives.

The Personal Employment and Services Office (PESO) strengthens and expands its employment services by facilitating the service machinery of the government, particularly at the state and local levels, and mapping the skills of PSUD program graduates, which will serve as the basis for their job or career placement when they are ready to do so.

The business sector strengthens its programs by continuing to advocate for implementing CBRP. Collaborate with the LGU when it has employees participating in the program, and provide help in any way possible.

The community support groups, such as the chairman and SK Federation president, and civil society organizations must work together to accomplish the following: comply with the barangay councils by assisting the needs of the participants from their respective barangays by preparing their meals and snacks; monitor the movement of illegal drugs in the barangay; and report on monthly activity.

The Service Provider- Recovery Service Group (RSG) performs its responsibilities such as disseminating information through symposia centered on the nature of addiction and the vicious cycle of co-dependence, facilitating the daily administration of the modules they have developed for the CBRP, serving as recovery companions for the recovering clients in collaboration with the Social Worker of the MSWDO. Further, it supervises the daily operations of the CBRP, serves as a facilitator, and shares the load of resolving difficulties and concerns arising from the program's implementation.

The government and non-government organizations may work hand-in-hand to include training related to family and its role in drug prevention. As for drug surrenderers, livelihood programs are preferred since they help them become financially independent.

It is recommended that Bukidnon State University initiates an extension program to serve drug surrenderers, like a comprehensive rehabilitation program that aims to provide counseling and therapy, skills training (job skills training, vocational education, and career development services), education (educational resources and classes), social support (peer support groups, mentorship programs, and other community building activities), health and wellness services (physical and mental health screening services and wellness programs), and legal and financial assistance (legal counseling and financial management resources) composed of a multidisciplinary team of professionals and community partners to ensure effective delivery of services and support.

Future researchers should replicate the study in other research locale and conduct a comparative study to explore the various social support, programs, services, and interventions using quantitative and qualitative data to understand the phenomenon using these methods. Future researchers may focus on the following areas to enhance the sustainability of the program: collaborate with community stakeholders, address personal and social issues, train the workforce, set up a monitoring and evaluation system, and promote sustainability.

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